

OPTIMIZING RADIO FREQUENCY ENERGY HARVESTING
WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORK USING PREDICTION
MODELLING AND ENERGY MANAGEMENT

BIKRANT KOIRALA

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

2021

Dedicated to my late grandmother, whose struggles and sacrifices have always encouraged me to stay positive and determined even during the most challenging times in my life

Abstract

The advent of energy harvesting technologies has paved the way for self-sustainable wireless sensor networks (WSNs). Lately, radio frequency (RF) energy harvesting WSN has been gaining attention due to its ability to power sensor nodes by tapping ambient RF energy. However, the uncertain availability and small amount of energy harvested from RF sources demand a prudent and robust energy management system for optimum network performance. Various works have focused on improving energy utilization for conventional energy harvesting networks. However, little effort has been put to address the energy management issues for RF powered WSNs. To address the issue, this work encompasses modelling of RF energy harvester, inception of a novel multi-node energy prediction technique and development of a fuzzy-based energy management system (FEMS) for RF energy harvesting WSNs. Results show that the proposed energy management system contributes in increasing the sensor node's lifetime by 30% while reducing the energy buffer size by 10%.

Acknowledgements

I have to admit that while finalizing this thesis, I find myself in the place of the young lawyer from the short story, *The Bet* by Anton Chekhov. In the last part of the story, the character reveals that the greatest prize is not the money he would receive by winning the bet but the knowledge and wisdom he had acquired during those fifteen years of solitude. I, too, feel that my most significant achievement is the set of skills I have developed and the valuable insights I have garnered during my journey as a research student, which would help me pursue my future endeavours.

For making my journey worthwhile and comfortable, I am sincerely indebted to my supervisor Professor Keshav Dahal, who committed his time and expertise to guide me throughout this research. Moreover, as a mentor, he always applauded my success and kept me motivated during my lows. I would also like to express my gratitude to my family members, friend, and relatives for their support and encouragement in all these years.

My deep appreciation goes to all those individuals who worked hard day and night without even caring for their own lives to save millions of people around the globe affected by the Covid-19 pandemic.

I thank the support provided by the EU Erasmus Mundus project, SmartLink (552077-EM-1-2014-1-UK-ERA), to carry out this research.

Contents

Abstract.....	III
Acknowledgements	IV
Contents	V
List of Tables	VIII
List of Figures	IX
List of Abbreviations	XII
Chapter 1 Introduction	1
1.1 Background	2
1.2 Motivation.....	4
1.3 Research Questions and Procedure	6
1.4 Main Contributions	9
1.5 Publications.....	10
1.6 Structure of the Thesis	11
Chapter 2 Literature Review	13
2.1 Ambient Energy Sources and Energy Harvesting	14
2.2 RF Energy Harvesting and Transport	17
2.3 RF Energy Harvesting in Sensor Networks	24
2.4 Protocols and Energy Management in EH Networks	26
2.4.1 Energy Management	26
2.4.2 Energy Transfer Techniques	30
2.4.3 Data Delivery, Routing and MAC Protocols	31

2.5 Use of Energy Prediction in Energy Management	38
2.6 Summary and Research Gap	43
Chapter 3 RF Energy Harvester Modelling	46
3.1 Introduction.....	47
3.2 Related Works.....	49
3.3 RF Energy Harvester Model	50
3.4 RF Energy Harvester Simulation	55
3.4.1 Results and Discussion	55
3.5 Summary	60
Chapter 4 Energy Prediction Model and Prediction Interval	61
4.1 Introduction.....	62
4.2 Related Works.....	63
4.3 Energy Prediction Model and Prediction Interval	65
4.3.1 Multi-Node Energy Prediction Model	65
4.3.2 Optimum Energy Prediction Interval.....	67
4.4 Energy Prediction Model Simulation.....	70
4.5 Summary	77
Chapter 5 FEMS: A Fuzzy-Based Adaptive Energy Management System.....	79
5.1 Introduction.....	80
5.2 Related Works.....	81
5.3 Energy Management System Model.....	83
5.3.1 Rule Based Scheme.....	84
5.3.2 Fuzzy Energy Management System (FEMS)	85
5.3.3 LEACH Protocol.....	86
5.4 Energy Management System Simulation.....	87
5.4.1 FEMS Parameters	87
5.4.2 Network Parameters.....	88
5.4.3 Node Analysis and Duty Cycle.....	89
5.4.4 Buffer Capacity and Energy Usage.....	90
5.4.5 Network Performance	91
5.5 Summary	93

Chapter 6 Energy Management with Multi-Node Prediction	94
6.1 Introduction.....	95
6.2 System Description	97
6.2.1 Single Node Prediction	97
6.2.2 Multi Node Prediction.....	98
6.3 System Simulation	99
6.3.1 Single Node and Multi Node Prediction Parameters	100
6.3.2 Network Parameters.....	100
6.3.3 Node Analysis and Duty Cycle.....	101
6.3.4 Buffer Capacity and Energy Usage.....	103
6.3.5 Network Performance	104
6.4 Summary	106
Chapter 7 Summary, Observations and Conclusions, and Future Works.....	108
7.1 Summary	109
7.2 Observations and Conclusions	110
7.3 Future Works	113
7.3.1 RF Energy Harvester Model and Multiple Energy Sources	113
7.3.2 Use of Prediction Error in Energy Management.....	114
7.3.3 Applicability of the Developed Models for other EH Systems	116
References.....	116

List of Tables

Table 2.1 Ambient Energy Sources	15
Table 2.2 Experimental Data of RF Energy Harvesting	19
Table 2.3 Power Consumption Data for Energy Monitoring Sensors	27
Table 2.4 Energy Management Technique Comparison for Harvesting Systems	39
Table 3.1 MATLAB Simulation Parameters	55
Table 3.2 NS-2.35 Simulation Parameters.....	59
Table 4.1 Simulation Parameters	70
Table 4.2 Actual and Predicted Energy for Prediction Interval of 60s	71
Table 4.3 MAPE Summary Table.....	73
Table 5.1 Inference Rules	85
Table 5.2 FEMS Parameters	87
Table 5.3 WSN Parameters.....	88
Table 5.4 Average Dead Nodes	92
Table 6.1 Multi-Node Parameters.....	100
Table 6.2 Prediction Errors for Single and Multi-Node Predictions	100
Table 6.3 WSN Parameters.....	101
Table 6.4 Average Dead Nodes	105

List of Figures

Figure 1.1 Research Tasks	7
Figure 2.1 Block Diagram of an Energy Harvesting Wireless Sensor Platform	16
Figure 2.2 Wireless RF Power System	17
Figure 2.3 RF and Microwave-Energy Conversion Efficiencies.....	19
Figure 2.4 General Architecture of RF Energy Harvesting Network	21
Figure 3.1 Block Diagram of a RF-EH System	47
Figure 3.2 Optimal Energy Consumption Rate and Buffer Ratio for Variation of 0.1.....	56
Figure 3.3 Optimal Energy Consumption Rate and Buffer Ratio for Variation of 0.5.....	56
Figure 3.4 Optimal Energy Consumption Rate and Buffer Ratio for Variation of 0.9.....	57
Figure 3.5 Optimal Energy Consumption Rate Variation with Source-Harvester Separation Distance.....	57
Figure 3.6 Buffer Ratio Variation with Source-Harvester Separation Distance.....	58
Figure 3.7. Network Lifetime for Different Values of Energy Consumption Rates.....	59
Figure 3.8. Buffer Capacity for Different Values of Energy Consumption Rates.....	59
Figure 3.9. Lifetimes of Sensor Nodes with Optimal Energy Consumption Rate.....	59
Figure 4.1 Multi-Node Energy Prediction Model.....	62
Figure 4.2 Node ‘A’ with Neighbouring Nodes	65
Figure 4.3 Time Frame Showing Prediction Instances	65
Figure 4.4 Prediction Interval with Sleep and Active States	68

Figure 4.5 Simulation Layout-1 for Multi-Node Prediction.....	70
Figure 4.6 Actual and Predicted Energy for Prediction Interval of 60s (for layout-1).....	72
Figure 4.7 Actual and Predicted Energy for Prediction Interval of 30s (for layout-1).....	72
Figure 4.8 Actual and Predicted Energy for Prediction Interval of 60s (for layout-2).....	73
Figure 4.9 Actual and Predicted Energy for Prediction Interval of 30s (for layout-2).....	73
Figure 4.10 Neighbouring Node Usage Percentage for Different Prediction Intervals (for layout-1).....	74
Figure 4.11 Neighbouring Node Usage Percentage for Different Prediction Intervals (for layout-2).....	74
Figure 4.12 MAPE for Various Prediction Intervals (for layout-1).....	75
Figure 4.13 Prediction Intervals for Different Threshold Values	76
Figure 4.14 Variations of Remaining Energy and Threshold Energy against Prediction Interval for Various Values of Threshold Constant	76
Figure 5.1 Fuzzy-Based Energy Management System Model.....	80
Figure 5.2 Frame Structure with Active and Sleep States	83
Figure 5.3 Rule-Based Scheme.....	84
Figure 5.4 Predicted Energy Member Functions	85
Figure 5.5 Buffer Charge Member Functions.....	85
Figure 5.6 Energy Budget Member Function	86
Figure 5.7 Surface Generation of the FIS	86
Figure 5.8 Network Implementation using LEACH Protocol	88
Figure 5.9 Duty Cycle Comparison	89
Figure 5.10 Node Analysis	90
Figure 5.11 Buffer Charge Comparison and Harvested Energy	90
Figure 5.12 Dead Nodes Comparison (for n=100)	91

Figure 5.13 Data Loss and Network Life Comparison	92
Figure 6.1 Fuzzy Based Energy Management using Single-Node Prediction.....	95
Figure 6.2 Fuzzy Based Energy Management using Multi-Node Prediction	96
Figure 6.3 Node Layout for Multi-Node Prediction	98
Figure 6.4 Frame Structure	98
Figure 6.5 Duty Cycle Comparison for Prediction Interval of 10 seconds.....	101
Figure 6.6 Duty Cycle Comparison for Prediction Interval of 30 seconds.....	101
Figure 6.7 Node Analysis for Prediction Interval of 10 seconds.....	102
Figure 6.8 Node Analysis for Prediction Interval of 30 seconds.....	102
Figure 6.9 Buffer Charge Comparison for Prediction Interval of 10 seconds.....	103
Figure 6.10 Buffer Charge Comparison for Prediction Interval of 30 seconds.....	103
Figure 6.11 Dead Nodes Comparison for Prediction Interval of 10 seconds	104
Figure 6.12 Dead Nodes Comparison for Prediction Interval of 30 seconds	105
Figure 6.13 Data Loss Comparison for Prediction Interval of 10 seconds.....	105
Figure 6.14 Data Loss Comparison for Prediction Interval of 30 seconds.....	106
Figure 7.1 Improving Energy Management using Prediction Error	114

List of Abbreviations

AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
CSMA	Collision Sense Multiple Access
DA	Device Agnostic
DFS	Dynamic Frequency Scaling
DS	Device Specific
DVS	Dynamic Voltage Scaling
EA-MAC	Energy Adaptive Medium Access Control
EH	Energy Harvesting
EM	Electromagnetic
ENO	Energy Neutral Operation
ET	Energy Transmitter
EWMA	Exponentially Weighted Moving Average
FEMS	Fuzzy-Based Energy Management System
FF	Far Field
FIS	Fuzzy Inference System
FLC	Fuzzy Logic Controller
HAPM	Harvesting Aware Power Management
IoT	Internet of Things

ISM	Industry-Science-Medical
LEACH	Low Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy
MA	Moving Average
MAC	Medium Access Control
MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error
MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking
NF	Near Field
ODMAC	On Demand Medium Access Control
PMU	Power Management Unit
QoS	Quality of Service
RF	Radio Frequency
RF-EHN	Radio Frequency Energy Harvesting Network
RFID	Radio-Frequency Identification
SDR	Software-Defined Radio
SMA	Simple Moving Average
TDMA	Time Division Multiple Access
UHF	Ultrahigh-frequency
WATS	Wireless Autonomous Transducer System
WCMA	Weather Conditioned Moving Average
WEH	Wireless Energy Harvesting
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network

Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter explains the motivation to carry out the research work and a brief background on the research topic. It also highlights the research questions this work aims to answer, followed by the description of the overall research procedure. The contributions made in terms of research publications are also listed. Further, a short explanation providing an overview of the content of the thesis at the end is also presented.

1.1 Background

At present, there have been growing research interests in radio frequency (RF) energy harvesting techniques, which can convert the received RF signals into electricity. Conventionally, the energy-constrained wireless networks, such as wireless sensor networks (WSNs), have a limited lifetime which largely confines the network performance. In contrast, an RF energy harvesting network (RF-EHN) has a sustainable power supply from a radio environment. Therefore, RF energy harvesting capability allows wireless devices to harvest energy from RF signals for information processing and transmission (Lu et al., 2015b). RF energy harvesting provides critical benefits in terms of being wireless, readily available in the form of transmitted energy (TV/radio broadcasters, mobile base stations, handheld radios and dedicated RF energy sources), low cost, and small form factor implementation (Kamalinejad et al., 2015). In RF energy harvesting, radio signals with a frequency range from 300 GHz to as low as 3 kHz can be used as a medium to carry energy in the form of electromagnetic radiation (Lu et al., 2015a).

In RF energy harvesting WSNs, the amount of the harvested energy depends on the type of RF source and the distance between the energy harvesting sensor nodes and the source. In a WSN, there are a large number of nodes, each positioned in a different location. The nodes nearer to the source harvests a higher amount of energy compared to the nodes far away. Therefore, a dynamic and adaptive energy balancing mechanism is required to maintain the acceptable performance of the WSN as compared to battery-powered counterparts. For RF energy harvesting WSNs, the position or the placement of the energy harvesting nodes is also an important design aspect as the RF waves from a source (or different sources) may interfere with each other resulting in the formation of the zones with very high or almost zero energy levels.

RF energy harvesting in WSNs introduces RF energy harvesting as a new function for wireless devices. The design issues are energy management, data delivery scheme, topology and connectivity, and energy storage technology (Zahid Kausar et al., 2014, Lu et al., 2015a). Energy management is one of the main issues in designing energy harvesting networks. It deals with the proper utilisation of the scavenged RF energy to ensure a fully stand-alone system. In a WSN, power management policy works closely with hardware and various protocols concerned with routing and medium access addressing needs such as energy-neutral operation (ENO), power balancing among nodes and storage limit/capacity.

Uncertain availability of ambient RF energy poses a challenge for developing an energy-efficient energy management system. The issues can be handled properly if the future energy availability can be predicted and the system's energy utilisation is optimised according to the behaviour of the energy sources over short and medium time frames. This will ensure exploiting at best the available energy, minimizing the likelihood that essential tasks are not executed due to lack of energy and decreasing energy waste in cases where the harvested energy is neither used nor stored (Cammarano et al., 2012). The other importance of the prediction lies in the fact that if the amount of energy to be harvested in the future is known in advance, proper energy management can be done considering remaining stored energy, energy consumption rate and routing of information, ensuring optimal quality of service (QoS) and network life-time.

1.2 Motivation

For any energy harvesting (EH) system to optimize energy utilisation and minimize waste, the system needs to operate as per the energy profile of the source. Moreover, its design should consider load and harvester properties (Pimentel and Musilek, 2010). Energy neutrality is a condition for an EH system to operate perpetually, i.e., for energy neutral operation (ENO), the energy used should always be less than the energy harvested. It is necessary to develop a model for RF powered WSNs to determine the energy consumption rate for various associated source energy levels, ensuring continuous work of applications with minimal energy wastage even in worst-case scenarios. It should also apply to diverse ambient conditions. In addition, the relation between harvested energy, consumed energy and energy buffer size defined by the model should be able to represent the network's optimal performance scenario (Kansal et al., 2007).

There has been significant research in the area of prediction-based energy management for EH networks. One such work presented in (Kansal et al., 2007) describes an energy-neutral and adaptive duty cycling algorithm based on an exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA) energy prediction model. Similarly, a prediction algorithm based on weather conditions is described in (Piorno et al., 2009) for solar-based energy harvesting. Likewise, another prediction model, termed Pro-Energy, developed for solar and wind energy harvesting WSNs is described in (Cammarano et al., 2012). However, as RF energy suffers from reflection, diffraction, interference, scattering and others, its magnitude varies within small distances (Visser and Vullers, 2013). These characteristics can be exploited in devising a prediction model for RF-EH WSNs. Also, the research works described above do not provide sufficient insight for estimating an optimum prediction interval, which is crucial in developing prediction-based energy management systems.

Despite of its advantages, RF powered WSN inherits two significant challenges affecting its overall performance. First, the uncertain availability of the ambient RF energy and second, efficient utilization of a small amount of energy harvested from RF power sources (Basagni et al., 2013, Baroudi, 2019). Various works on energy harvesting WSN based on wind and solar have adopted prediction based energy management techniques to optimize the network's energy utilization. The pre-knowledge of energy availability helps manage and adjust network parameters in advance, ensuring optimal network performance (Baroudi, 2019, Cammarano et al., 2016). However, as RF energy varies significantly within a short period (Visser and Vullers, 2013), developing a prudent and robust energy management technique becomes crucial for RF-powered WSN.

In this regard, this study mainly focuses on three aspects - modelling, prediction method and energy management system for RF energy harvesting WSN. RF energy harvesting systems differ from other energy harvesting types. The amount of harvested energy depends on the parameters like source-harvester separation, RF frequency, signal interference, and the surrounding conditions. These parameters are set to be accommodated while developing the RF energy harvester model. Prediction models are often coupled with energy management policies to ensure optimal network performance. To devise an RF energy specific prediction method, the characteristic of RF energy needs to be exploited to formulate a prediction scheme applicable for RF energy harvesting sensor networks. The final objective would be to integrate the developed prediction method with a robust and dynamic energy management system, ensuring optimal network performance.

1.3 Research Questions and Procedure

The research aims to devise an efficient prediction-based energy management technique for RF energy harvesting WSNs. In other words, this work incorporates formulation of an energy management scheme that would work with the prediction model to adjust and regulate the energy flow ensuring a self-sufficient stand-alone WSNs with optimum network performance.

In particular, this work attempts to answer the following questions:

1. Are there any additional parameters (compared to conventional energy harvesting sources such as solar or wind) that need to be considered for developing the RF energy harvester model?
2. Can a balance between energy harvesting and load energy consumption rates be achieved to maintain ENO and minimum energy wastage (or loss)? Also, is there an optimum buffer capacity (size) for such a balanced state?
3. Can a prediction method unique to RF energy harvester with enhanced performance be devised?
4. How does the conventional prediction-based energy management technique perform when used with RF energy harvesting sensor networks?
5. Is there a better energy management scheme that would ensure efficient energy utilization in RF powered sensor nodes?

To answer the above questions, first, RF energy harvester model is conceptualized based on which an energy prediction approach and energy management system are developed. Presented next is the detailed research tasks.

Figure 1.1 Research Tasks

As depicted in Figure 1.1, this research work is segregated into three main tasks viz. model development, the conception of energy prediction scheme and design of prediction-based energy management system for RF energy harvesting WSNs. The model, largely a mathematical formulation, provides optimal parameter values to build on both the prediction method and management unit. In addition, modelling becomes necessary to make sure that the developed prediction and energy management techniques incorporate energy neutral operation (ENO) and minimum energy wastage of harvested energy. RF energy harvester modelling is covered in Chapter 3. Section 3.4 of the chapter presents the simulation parameters and the obtained results. The simulation work is divided into two parts. First, the developed model is used to compute the optimum energy consumption rate and buffer capacity. For this, a single RF energy source of frequency 2.45 GHz is considered. Second, the network's life-time for the obtained optimum energy consumption rate is evaluated.

The RF-EH specific prediction method exploits the characteristic of RF energy to improve the prediction quality. The simulation of the developed multi-node energy prediction technique is detailed in Chapter 4, which considers a single RF source with an omni-directional antenna and with the sinusoidal impulse response. An additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channel is linked with the individual sensor nodes to provide the effect of the random process. Observations are made for each layout with four and eight nodes surrounding a centre node. This has been detailed in Section 4.4 of the chapter.

Finally, the energy management scheme uses energy prediction to optimise energy utilization for improving the overall network's performance. Chapter 5 adopts a similar simulation set-up as in Chapter 4. Moreover, the experiment also utilizes the prediction interval model formulated in Section 4.3. Chapter 6 further extends the simulation incorporating multi-node energy prediction.

In each of the chapters mentioned above, simulation settings, along with their objectives, have been clearly mentioned. Moreover, the results of the experiments have been analysed, and conclusions are drawn.

1.4 Main Contributions

The significant contributions of this thesis are summarised in the points below:

- A model for RF powered WSNs with RF energy-specific parameters encompassing energy neutral operation (ENO) and buffer requirements has been developed (Chapter 3). The work is published in [3] with a revised version in [2].
- A novel multi-node energy prediction technique, which predicts the future energy availability by considering the harvesting history of all nodes surrounding the main node, has been conceived and its performance compared and evaluated (Chapter 4). Published in [1].
- A fuzzy-based energy management system (FEMS) for RF powered wireless sensor networks is designed and implemented (Chapter 5). The management technique utilizes a fuzzy inference system with buffer charge level and harvested energy forecast as its inputs. Results show that FEMS improves the network's lifetime, reduces data loss, and requires a smaller buffer size than the conventional rule-based approach.

1.5 Publications

The work in this thesis has also been reported in the publications listed below. The experiments were designed and conducted by the candidate along with the writing up of papers. At the same time, co-authors of the papers have provided feedback on the idea and corrected the drafts.

- [1] B. Koirala, K. Dahal, P. Keir, and W. Chen, "A Multi-node Energy Prediction Approach Combined with Optimum Prediction Interval for RF Powered WSNs," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 24, p. 5551, 2019.
- [2] B. Koirala and K. Dahal, "Life-time and Buffer-size Optimization for RF Powered Wireless Sensor Networks," in *SENSORNETS 2019*, Prague, Czech Republic, 2019.
- [3] B. Koirala and K. Dahal, "Modelling and Analysis of RF Energy Harvesting Systems for Optimal Energy Consumption," in *SEEP 2018*, Paisley, UK, 2018.

1.6 Structure of the Thesis

The thesis is structured as follows:

This chapter (Chapter 1) explains the motivation behind the work along with research questions and aggregated research procedure. It also highlights the research contributions.

Chapter 2 details a literature review of research works encompassing energy harvesting technologies and management techniques of the harvested energy in sensor networks. It also explores literatures detailing various design aspects, techniques and protocols related to energy harvesting networks. Moreover, it also looks into the new and evolving paradigm of prediction based energy management systems and their applicability in energy harvesting devices.

Chapter 3 presents a model for RF powered WSNs that uses available RF energy encompassing energy neutral operation (ENO) and buffer requirements. An algorithm based on the model is developed to find each sensor node's optimum energy consumption rate that would ensure the maximum lifetime of the WSN with minimum buffer capacity. Additionally, it also accommodates the observations made to determine the effect of ambient conditions on consumption rate and buffer requirements.

Chapter 4 incorporates a novel multi-node energy prediction method for radio frequency energy harvesting (RF-EH) WSNs, which predicts the future energy availability by considering the harvesting history of all nodes surrounding the main node. It also presents a mathematical model to compute the optimum value of prediction interval, which has a significant effect on prediction accuracy and system design.

Chapter 5 deals with designing of a fuzzy-based adaptive energy management system - FEMS for RF energy harvesting systems. FEMS utilizes buffer charge level and harvested energy

forecast to implement adaptive duty cycling for individual nodes. The chapter also presents FEMS's network implementation using low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) protocol and its performance comparison with conventional rule-based energy management scheme.

Chapter 6 presents a multi-node prediction based FEMS and compares its performance with FEMS utilising single-node prediction approach for varying prediction intervals. Multi-node prediction method utilizes energy readings from neighbouring nodes to estimate the future energy availability, unlike the single-node approach, which forecasts the energy based only on its own historical data.

Finally, Chapter 7 concludes the thesis by providing a summary of the accomplishments and presents some conclusions and future works in this area of research.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

This chapter presents the research works encompassing energy harvesting technologies and management techniques of the harvested energy in sensor networks. Literatures detailing with various design aspects, techniques and protocols related to energy harvesting networks have also been explored. Further, this chapter delves into the new and evolving paradigm of prediction based energy management systems and their applicability in this work. This research attempts to develop a model and energy management scheme suitable for RF energy harvesting technology. Wherever applicable, current systems' state of the art is explored and possible future research has been identified in them.

2.1 Ambient Energy Sources and Energy Harvesting

A wireless sensor network (WSN) is a group of sensing nodes connected through wireless channels to gather distributed data from their environment (Zahid Kausar et al., 2014). WSN provides better data quality than the individual sensor in various applications, such as process or environment monitoring, security and surveillance (Stojmenovic, 2005, Gilbert and Balouchi, 2008). Recently, the battery technology performance is much improved along with the reduction of power requirement for electronics (Zahid Kausar et al., 2014). However, these advancements are not enough to maintain with the speed of increasing demands of various applications of WSN. So, there is growing interest in developing systems capable of extracting necessary energy from different ambient sources. Such energy harnessing process is termed as energy harvesting (Gilbert and Balouchi, 2008).

Currently, energy harvesting systems that extract energy from ambient energy sources like solar, wind, vibration, electromagnetic waves, have garnered significant interest. Energy harvesting devices, which include energy harvesting devices, topologies and circuits, have been developed for self-sustainable standalone systems (Kim et al., 2014).

Table 2.1 summarizes commonly used ambient energy sources. One of the most commonly used ambient sources is solar power with a high power density of $100\text{mW}/\text{cm}^2$ during the daytime. However, due to low conversion efficiency of 10%-40%, a solar panel requires a relatively larger area to collect sufficient solar energy and is also the efficiency drops significantly on a cloudy day. Thermal energy is also widely used, which exploits the temperature difference in thermoelectric devices to generate electric power. A thermoelectric setup generates an energy density of $20\text{-}60\ \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ when it uses the human body as a heat source at room temperature of $18\ ^\circ\text{C}\text{-}25\ ^\circ\text{C}$. Thermoelectric harvesting devices typically require relatively large form factors to generate applicable amounts of power. The piezoelectric effect

produces electrical power from mechanical strains, such as vibration, pressure or deformation. Nominal output density values are around $250 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^3$, but more power can be created when motion or deformation is increased and the output power has a significant dynamic range when irregular motions, such as human movements, are used as the driving force. Though ambient radio frequency (RF) energy has a comparatively low energy density of about $0.2 \text{ nW}/\text{cm}^2$ - $1 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$, considerable amount of energy can be harvested by utilizing a high gain antenna (Kim et al., 2014).

Table 2.1 Ambient Energy Sources (Kim et al., 2014)

	Solar Energy	Thermal Energy	Ambient RF Energy	Piezoelectric Energy	
				Vibration	Push Button
Power Density	100 mW/cm ²	60 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$	0.0002–1 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$	200 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^3$	50 $\mu\text{J}/\text{N}$
Output	0.5 V (single Si cell) 1.0 V (single a-Si cell)	-	3 – 4 V (Open circuit)	10 – 25 V	10 – 1000 V
Available Time	Day time (4-8 Hrs)	Continuous	Continuous	Activity dependent	Activity dependent
Weight	5 - 10 g	10 – 20 g	2 – 3 g	2 – 10 g	1 – 2 g
Pros	-Large amount of energy -Well developed tech.	Always available	-Antenna can be integrated onto frame -Widely available	-Well developed tech. -Light weight	-Well developed tech. -Light weight Small volume
Cons	-Need large area -Non-continuous -Orientation issue	-Need large area -Low power -Rigid & brittle	-Distance dependent -Depending on available power source	-Need large area -Highly variable output	-Highly variable output -Low conversion efficiency (high volt/low amps.)

Figure 2.1 Block Diagram of an Energy Harvesting Wireless Sensor Platform (Kim et al., 2014)

A general block diagram of energy-harvesting enabled wireless sensor platform is shown in Figure 2.1. A converter or transducer is used to transform the ambient energy to the electrical energy stored in energy storage devices such as battery or super capacitors. The function of a power management unit (PMU) is to optimize the harvested energy by load impedance matching and by optimizing the duty cycle in energy efficient way (Pimentel and Musilek, 2010). The primary power source (battery or capacitor) lifetime can be prolonged by implementing energy-harvesting systems that can effectively recharge the main power periodically. If there is sufficient energy to run the whole system autonomously, the primary power source can be removed.

2.2 RF Energy Harvesting and Transport

It has not been long that the potential of RF energy harvesting has been recognized for powering low power consuming electronic devices. Despite there are other ambient sources such as solar, thermal, pressure and others. RF energy has its advantage of being omnipresent in today's modern era of wireless communication. Also, the implementation of an RF energy harvesting system in sensor networks is suitable due to its small form factor and reliability. Many experiments have been performed to demonstrate the feasibility and practicability of RF energy harvesting from ambient sources and using the harvested energy to power low power consuming electronic devices. Some of the experiments are discussed below.

Figure 2.2 Wireless RF Power System (Visser and Vullers, 2013)

Based on Maxwell's theory of electromagnetics, the first experiments on RF energy transmission were performed by Heinrich Hertz in 1880. Later works on RF free-space power transmission can be found to begin in late 1950 (Brown, 1984). In 1980 and 1990, interest was regained in this field by introducing radio-frequency identification (RFID) applications, particularly on the available industry-science-medical (ISM) frequency bands around 0.9, 2.4, 5.8 GHz, and higher. The wavelengths are shorter for higher frequencies so that it becomes

possible to realize smaller wireless autonomous transducer systems (WATSSs). WATSSs can be powered by incident RF radiation. An antenna and a rectifier is connected to form a rectenna, which transforms the incident RF energy into usable electrical energy. The electrical energy will pass through the energy storage device before it is passed on to the load, as in Figure 2.2 (Visser and Vullers, 2013). Far-field RF energy transmission, which differs from (close contact) inductive or non-radiative RF energy transmission, can be categorized into two types. RF energy harvesting and RF energy transport. Considering Figure 2.2, if ambient RF energy is used as a source, it is referred to as RF energy harvesting. If a dedicated RF energy source is employed, it is termed RF energy transport.

Ambient RF energy has a comparatively lower energy density of $0.2 \text{ nW/cm}^2 - 1 \text{ } \mu\text{W/cm}^2$ than other energy sources. However, significant amount of energy can be harvested using an antenna with higher gain. The availability of ambient RF energy density has been in a rise due to the increasing number of wireless communication devices and infrastructures, such as analogue/digital television, AM/FM radio, Wi-Fi routers, and cell phone networks. The ambient RF power density is generally higher in urban than in suburban areas (Piñuela et al., 2013). The RF energy harvesting technologies could prove useful in charging a battery or to provide power to electronic systems wirelessly in scenarios where it is difficult to replace or recharge batteries manually, like in structure such as bridges or buildings. It is also applicable when the wireless sensor networks are implemented in areas hard to access, like chemical/nuclear plants, aircraft or inside human/animal bodies in the form of implants (Zahid Kausar et al., 2014, Kim et al., 2014).

As the input power levels are very low (from -30 to -20 dBm), the conversion efficiency of the rectifier circuits to convert RF energy to electrical energy is only about 10% to 30%. However, the harvested RF energy can generate around 1.8 - 4.0 V resulting in a total converted power

level of about $100 \mu\text{W}$. This power is enough to operate sensors (with rechargeable battery) sporadically for more than five years. The harvested RF energy gets more prominent as gain of antenna and energy density of the ambient environment increase because the RF to dc conversion efficiency is improved (Kim et al., 2014).

Table 2.2 Experimental Data of RF Energy Harvesting (Lu et al., 2015b)

Source	Source Power	Frequency	Distance	Energy Harvested Rate
Isotropic RF transmitter	4W	902-928 MHz	15m	$5.5 \mu\text{W}$
Isotropic RF transmitter	1.78W	868 MHz	25m	$2.3 \mu\text{W}$
Isotropic RF transmitter	1.78W	868 MHz	27m	$2 \mu\text{W}$
TX91501 Powercaster transmitter	3W	915 MHz	5m	$189 \mu\text{W}$
TX91501 Powercaster transmitter	3W	915 MHz	11m	$1 \mu\text{W}$
KING-TV tower	960KW	674-680 MHz	4.1km	$60 \mu\text{W}$

Figure 2.3 RF and Microwave-Energy Conversion Efficiencies (Valenta and Durgin, 2014)

Table 2.2 shows the amount of RF energy harvested from various ambient sources obtained experimentally. It can be noted that the energy harvesting rate varies significantly with source power and distance. Normally, the amount of harvested energy is in order of microwatts, which is sufficient for powering small devices.

Figure 2.3 shows a survey of efficiencies for energy harvesting devices. The device efficiencies use various technologies and topologies and use varying loads due to their uses in wireless power transfer. These works cover frequencies from 800 MHz to 94 GHz but focus on work in the US ISM bands at 900 MHz, 2.4 GHz, and 5.8 GHz. In Figure 2.3, as power increases, efficiency also increases, this is due to decrease in losses caused by rectification diode threshold voltage. At high powers, significant efficiencies are possible, and as the power level is reduced, the device efficiency decreases because the diode is "on" for a smaller fraction of the RF wave period. On the other hand, as frequency increases, the efficiency of the device decreases. This is observed due to the parasitic losses encountered at microwave frequencies.

Figure 2.4 shows the block diagram of an RF energy harvesting network node, which consists of the following main components:

- An application performing some network function.
- A microcontroller to process data.
- An RF transceiver for information transmission/reception.
- An RF energy harvester consisting of an RF antenna, and circuitry to convert the harvested energy into usable electrical energy.
- A power management module, which regulates the energy obtained from the RF energy.

- An energy buffer or storage to store the harvested RF energy for future use.

Figure 2.4 General Architecture of RF Energy Harvesting Network (Lu et al., 2015a)

The power management module can utilize two different techniques to regulate the energy utilization, which are harvest-use and harvest-store-use. In the harvest-use technique, the harvested energy is used immediately to power the sensor node. Therefore, for the network node to operate normally, the converted electricity has to exceed the minimum energy requirement of the node or the node will die (run out of energy). The sensor node is equipped with an energy storage device (rechargeable battery or capacitor), which stores the converted electricity in the harvest-store-use technique. In case the harvested energy is more than the energy consumed by the node, the excess energy is stored in the energy buffer for future use (Lu et al., 2015b, Lu et al., 2015a).

Recently, many works has been proposed using RF signals for transporting energy along with information transfer. Simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) is a design paradigm in which information could also be jointly transmitted with energy using the identical waveform. Therefore, SWIPT designs also contributes in saving frequency (spectrum) usage. This is possible because any spectrum carrying information to be transmitted also carries energy, which can be harvested by the receivers. However, a SWIPT scheme with optimal

performance involves a trade-off between data and energy transfer/receive rate to balance the information decoding and energy harvesting efficiency. Therefore, optimizing wireless information and energy transfer both at the same time brings about a trade-off on the design of a wireless system, which demands redesign of current wireless networks (Lu et al., 2015b, Lu et al., 2015a, Bi et al., 2015).

In (Olgun et al., 2012), the authors propose an RF energy harvesting system that can harvest low-level ambient RF energy to power a sensor system from a typical Wi-Fi router (with transmitting power 100 mW) at short distance. The wide application of Wi-Fi and its operating frequency at 2.45 GHz band (as Bluetooth, ZigBee, RFID, cordless phone and others) makes it suitable for ambient RF energy harvesting. They have presented a rectifier circuit using a small rectenna that improves harvesting performance. Moreover, they have also devised a power management system, which minimises leakage and provides uninterrupted energy to the sensors. For rectenna design, the authors adopted a modified version of a single-stage full-wave Greinacher rectifier. Moreover, a 3 x 3 planar array of simple Koch-type patch antennas were adopted to produce sufficient dc power for the range of input power levels. For energy management, integrated circuits called S882Z and AS1310, which is a hysteric step-up dc-dc converter that has an ultra-low quiescent current ($<1 \mu\text{A}$), were used to step up and regulate the output voltage. Therefore, it can be operational even when the harvested dc voltage is as small as 7.0 V. S882Z is a charge pump IC that improves the performance of any step-up dc-dc converter. The ambient RF harvesting system was tested in a practical office environment (with ambient Wi-Fi signals) by powering a temperature and humidity meter with an LCD. The final design was able to generate dc voltage even when the received power was as low as -40 dBm. In this paper (Olgun et al., 2012), the authors only present the RF energy harvesting prototype in a closed (indoor) environment and do not provide any insight regarding outdoor applications.

An RF energy harvester was realized in (Piñuela et al., 2013) that would operate at ambient RF power levels found in a city and suburb environments. A city-wide RF spectral study was conducted outside of all the 270 London Underground stations to explore the possibility for ambient RF energy harvesting. Based on the results, rectennas were designed and their efficiencies were calculated using in-situ field strength measurements. The spectral survey was conducted within the frequency band of 0.3 – 3 GHz, which covered four frequency bands from DTV, GSM900, GSM1800, and 3G. Prototypes were designed for each frequency band. It was demonstrated that single-band harvesters can operate with efficiencies of up to 40% with power levels as low as -25 dBm. Multiband array architectures were also investigated for operational flexibility. RF harvesting was achieved at an input RF power level as low as -29 dBm with additional current summing harvester arrays.

In (Costanzo et al., 2014), the authors presented a design to power devices using electromagnetic (EM) waves, located both in the near field (NF) and far-field (FF). Various prototypes and the obtained experimental results for FF and NF wireless power transfer systems are analysed. Specifically, two rectifying antennas are presented in FF systems viz. a wearable rectenna for ultrahigh-frequency (UHF) on clothing materials and a tetra-band rectenna for harvesting from GSM UMTS and Wi-Fi sources. Regarding NF wireless power systems, a wireless resonant energy link for energisation of the implanted medical devices (such as pacemakers, gastro stimulators, drug-delivery pumps, and others) and a harvester for compact fluorescent lamp are presented. Tests were conducted by an RF signal generated using a software-defined radio (SDR) platform. Measurement of the power density incident on the rectenna was carried out using the PMM 8053A broadband field meter with the EP-183 isotropic probe. It was found that the wireless link conditions were significantly variable when harvesting from ambient sources, and also the receiver could only can be optimised. Different antenna characteristics are required in FF wireless power transfer, viz. narrowband and

directive antennas are more suitable for intentional wireless power transfer. In contrast, harvesting from ambient sources requires multi-band, omnidirectional, and circularly polarised antennas.

2.3 RF Energy Harvesting in Sensor Networks

WSNs are collections of several sensor nodes that wirelessly communicate from the source node to the sink node. Sensor nodes are the perfect candidates for the implementation of RF energy harvesting since they consume very little power. It also means a long sustainable lifetime of the nodes without the need to replace batteries. Especially when WSNs are deployed in areas that are difficult to access for replacing or recharging batteries manually, RF energy harvesting provides a convenient solution.

Solar energy harvesting has been commonly used to overcome the barriers that prevent the real-world deployment of WSNs. However, it should be noted that solar powered WSNs suffer from energy shortages at night times. Therefore, to address this issue, the authors in (Nishimoto et al., 2010) utilize RF signals from TV broadcasts as energy sources to power WSN nodes. Specifically, the paper presents a prototype implementation of a WSN powered by RF energy harvesting using TV broadcast signals. It has been shown that the harvested energy is likely to vary in time and space. Hence, an adaptive duty cycle technique has been described to address the issue as mentioned earlier. In designing the system, the authors used the concept of energy-neutral operation, which states that the energy needed to charge and recharge decreases and the energy utilization efficiency increases when the duty cycle is tuned with the trend of harvested energy. From experimental evaluations, the authors find the rectifier's efficiency to be low for the lower input power level. The sensor node prototype test was performed at 500m away from

the Tokyo tower broadcasting TV signals over UHF frequency band. It was noted that since the RF energy harvester only harnesses power in terms of hundreds of microwatts while dozen of milliwatts of power is consumed for the data transmission, the sensor node needs wait for a specific time to charge the energy buffer. In other words, most energy harvesting WSNs consume a higher current than the charging current from the harvested energy. So, a power management system was required to monitor the harvested energy. An algorithm has been implemented in the system in order to balance the harvested power with the consumed power. The final developed prototype used a technique based on an adaptive duty cycle, which could sense and transmit temperature data every 5 seconds by utilizing RF energy harvesting.

RF signal propagation conditions have been experimentally investigated in (Visser and Vullers, 2012) for office and house environments. Wireless far-field RF energy is used to charge a rechargeable battery of a low power consuming wireless sensor node. Measurements for temperature and humidity are taken every 45 seconds and then transmitted to a base station. To estimate the maximum operating range for the RF battery charger, the authors measured the charging current as a function of distance between the battery charger and the RF source. The measurements were done for varying antenna types and transmitting powers at different heights from the ground. In addition, the measurements were also carried out for different office settings maintaining a line of sight between the transmitting and receiving antennas. The results showed that instead of boosting up the radiated power, an intelligent choice of transmitting antenna position and radiation pattern significantly helps in decreasing the distance of operation between the RF powered devices and RF energy source.

In internet of things (IoT) everyday physical objects, each unique identifier, are collected to the internet to form a structure without requiring human interaction. The authors in (Kamalinejad et al., 2015) proposed a power management unit (PMU) that comprises a battery

charging system using the harvested energy through a wireless energy harvesting (WEH) unit. Furthermore, they analysed the lifetime of the proposed WEH-IoT system for various IoT networked systems scenarios. The energy cost model is presented using both uniform and random distribution topology of sensor devices. An important aspect of any energy harvesting system is its energy management system, which controls the storage of the harvested energy. It also optimizes the usage of the available energy among various devices to maximise the lifetime while maintaining an acceptable QoS. The authors proposed a PMU which is capable of enabling practical cooperation with the WEH unit. The proposed design is an event-triggered or asynchronous technique based on the signal generated by a low-power wakeup radio (WUR). The PMU design also incorporates a failure detection mechanism, which pre-empts the failure of a node in case of energy deficiency.

2.4 Protocols and Energy Management in EH Networks

RF energy harvesting in WSNs introduces RF energy harvesting as a new function for wireless devices. As a result, resource allocation in RF energy harvesting must consider two objectives: information transmission/reception and RF energy harvesting. The design issues are energy management, data delivery scheme, topology and connectivity, and energy storage technology (Zahid Kausar et al., 2014, Lu et al., 2015a). These will be covered in the following sections.

2.4.1 Energy Management

Conventional energy management technique designed for battery-powered devices fails to accommodate the requirements of energy harvesting systems. Since the energy is extracted from the ambient environment, it means limited output power and also the energy source can vary, and availability of the energy can be virtually infinite. So, as to design a harvesting aware system, the authors in (Pimentel and Musilek, 2010) propose a proper harvesting aware power

management (HAPM) that allows a harvesting system to operate perpetually and maintaining the expected quality of service. The proposed HAPM mainly focuses on duty cycling, hardware with features such as Dynamic Voltage Scaling (DVS) and Dynamic Frequency Scaling (DFS). Duty cycling can be fixed or dynamic. The former is a simple approach but cannot cope with the energy source's abundant energy (more than it is consumed) or when energy production is less than energy consumption. For these cases, the latter is preferred despite the complexity. DVS and DFS are advanced power management techniques requiring specially designed hardware that can be utilized for HAPM. In DVS, increase in a circuit's voltage makes the switching faster but it causes the energy consumption to increase. The reverse happens for decrease in voltage. Similar phenomena can be expected for increase or decrease in clock frequency. The benefit of utilizing these techniques is that when the available energy is low, the system is allowed to run at a low speed and with minimal energy consumption making sure that all the crucial tasks are executed. In contrast, duty cycling completely halts all the activities during the sleeping mode. Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) is a technique, which allows maximum power transfer to the load. MPPT monitors the incoming energy to determine the optimal operation point and an adaptive load. The HAPM module decides whether to route more or less energy to the energy buffer (battery or capacitor) to estimate the duty cycling.

Table 2.3 Power Consumption Data for Energy Monitoring Sensors (Zahid Kausar et al., 2014)

Wireless product	Current consumption			Battery voltage (V)	Power consumption (mW)
	Transmission mode (mA)	Reception mode (mA)	Sleep mode		
RCS-S09U Universal ISM Band FSK Transceiver Module	15–26	11–15	150.3 mA	2.2–3.8	33–78
G-Link 2.4 GHz wireless Accelerometer Node (Micro Strain)	25	25	0.5 mA	2.7	92.5
IMOTE2 (Crossbow)	33	33	390 μ A	4.5	127.05

XBEE Zigbee/802.15.4 Modules (DigiInternational)	50	50	10 μ A	2.8–3.4	155
DataBridge wireless I/O modules	37–120	37–120	<100 μ A	2.7–3.6	116.55–378
Apex and Apex LT Modules	170	37	5 μ A	2.1–3.6	105.45–484.5
Lt Series Transceiver Module	12–14	12–14	11.5–20 μ A	2.1–3.6	34.2–39.9
Si4420 Universal ISM Band FSK Transceiver	13–26	11–5	0.3 μ A	2.2–5.4	41.8–98

For maximising the benefits of harvested energy, efficient power management is essential. Power consumption data for some standard energy monitoring sensors are presented in Table 2.3. Conventional battery-powered WSN differs significantly with the energy harvesting devices in WSN in terms of parameters that are used for power management. To fill the gap a power management system can be added between the harvesting source and the load to balance the energy consumption trend with the available generation profile (Zahid Kausar et al., 2014). The system must consider problems regarding prediction of future energy availability, including efficient power conversion techniques, scheduling, duty cycling, and others.

Hardware Requirements

Normally, for a given time the amount of energy consumed by an embedded system is more than the energy harvested from a source. Moreover, if the energy production is equal to or more than the energy consumption then for such scenario only a device can continuously. If this is not the case, i.e., if the consumption is higher than the production, a balance is required between them (Pimentel and Musilek, 2010), which can be achieved by utilizing harvesting compatible power management techniques in a hardware environment.

Duty Cycling

Duty cycling is a power management strategy that can be attributed to the fact that embedded systems or sensor networks frequently support sleep and active modes, making duty cycling a direct approach. Generally, the simple way to implement this technique is to set a fixed duty cycle matching the average energy consumption to the average energy production. On contrary, the duty cycle varies with the amount of energy harvested for dynamic duty cycling. A dynamic duty cycling approach can improve the overall system performance compared to its fixed counterpart (Pimentel and Musilek, 2010).

Topology and Connectivity

Power control is one of the important aspects for establishing connectivity over topology control. In case there is no continuous supply of sufficient harvested energy to power the sensor nodes, the nodes abandon all the activities and go to sleep mode for charging battery. This causes the network topology and connectivity to change. Various sleep and wakeup performance techniques depend on several factors such as channel conditions, battery level and ambience. Moreover, sensor nodes clustering scheme can be upgraded by taking into account behaviour of energy harvesting systems (Zahid Kausar et al., 2014).

Energy Storage Technology

It is difficult to replace the batteries for sensors implanted inside structures, like buildings and bridges, and moreover, they have limited recharge cycles, i.e. they cannot be recharged beyond a threshold. So, it is important to devise sensors with self-powered capabilities, which can sustain for a long time. Supercapacitors can be a substitute for rechargeable battery as they can be re-charged by energy harvesting devices in a similar fashion as the rechargeable batteries. One of the advantages of using supercapacitors is that the charge cycle is more than half a million with a functioning lifetime of ten years before the energy capacity is reduced to 80%.

Unlike ordinary capacitors, supercapacitors feature higher energy density with relatively smaller form factor, which is more suitable for WSNs than a regular capacitor (Zahid Kausar et al., 2014).

2.4.2 Energy Transfer Techniques

One of the significant limitations in a WSN is the dissipation of energy in the nodes and the node's energy buffer lifetime. In (Wafra et al., 2011), the authors have developed a technique to provide multi-hop wireless energy transfer protocol in WSNs, thus extending their lifetime till the functioning limits of their hardware. With the technique, the authors aim to charge critical nodes with efficiencies up to 40%. In this paper, three techniques for multi-hop wireless energy transfer are presented, along with individual efficiencies.

- *Store and Forward Technique:* In this technique each node is fitted with a rechargeable battery. The primary power source transfers energy to the nearer nodes, which they use eventually to charge their batteries. The wireless energy transfer is stopped once their batteries are full (or the source energy reaches a 50% threshold). Next, the nodes nearer to the source transfer the stored energy in their batteries to the nodes in next-hop and they then transmit it to the next-hop nodes in the next round.
- *Direct Flow Technique:* A single node can couple with multiple nodes simultaneously. This feature is exploited by direct flow technique. Each intermediate node couples with the preceding and succeeding nodes from the source node to the destination node. This node then directly transmits the energy (received from the previous node) to the following node without storing it in its battery.
- *Hybrid Technique:* For smaller number of nodes, the direct flow technique has better performance than store and forward. However, as the number of nodes increases the losses add up since, energy is being transmitted and received simultaneously. As a

consequence, the final node might be deprived of receiving any energy at all. To combat this problem, the hybrid technique combines advantages of both the store and forward and direct flow technique. When transmitting energy over a large number of hops it uses the direct flow technique so that there is no charging and discharging losses. In the hybrid technique, energy is transported utilizing the direct flow technique for a small number of hops n and then the energy is stored at the n^{th} node. It is then transferred to the following n^{th} node again using the direct flow technique.

The proposed multi-hop energy transfer technique provided an acceptable efficiency for energy transfer, and with an external energy source available, critical nodes 20 hops away could be charged wirelessly.

2.4.3 Data Delivery, Routing and MAC Protocols

The data delivery process from a sensor to the sink normally includes two main tasks: medium access and forwarding the information to the next step towards the sink. Energy conservation is the central objective of any protocols designed for WSN.

Medium Access Control (MAC) Protocol

A MAC protocol designed explicitly for RF energy harvesting networks needs to coordinate transmissions of network nodes. The network nodes also require to spend some time for RF energy harvesting along with channel access for information transfer. However, there are challenges such as the time taken for various nodes to harvest sufficient RF energy vary significantly due to their locations (nodes nearer to the source harvest more energy than the nodes far away). Typically, MAC protocols coordinate network nodes via two approaches - a contention-free (e.g. polling) or a contention-based (e.g. CSMA/CA). The contention-free MAC protocol takes into account the node-specific RF energy harvesting process to achieve high throughput and fairness. On the other hand, in the contention-based MAC protocol, each node contends for radio spectrum for information transfer (Lu et al., 2015b, Lu et al., 2015a).

Routing Protocol

The routing protocols in RF energy harvesting networks must consider the RF energy characteristics and the hardware design of sensor nodes (e.g. an RF energy harvester's sensitivity) unlike routing protocol developed for conventional WSN. In addition, the routing parameters need to be defined based on both RF energy harvesting matrices (e.g. RF signal strength, energy conversion rate, and RF sources-harvester separation) and network parameters (e.g. link quality and the number of hops) (Lu et al., 2015b, Lu et al., 2015a).

Cross-Layer Design

As the RF energy availability is uncertain and fluctuates with time, the WSN needs to operate in duty-cycled mode and also dynamically adjust its duty cycles to match the harvested RF energy profile. Dynamic duty cycles pose challenges in terms of synchronisation, reliability, efficiency of channel and energy utilization when designing MAC layer protocol. Hence, to address these issues there is a need of duty-cycling-aware middleware between MAC and physical (PHY) layer power management (Jurdak, 2007, Kamalinejad et al., 2015). An efficient wireless system design considers a cross-layer design approach, where PHY and MAC layers are closely related. Moreover, for efficient energy scheduling the residual battery life, wake up/sleep schedule, and estimated energy consumption of all network nodes should be taken into account (Vuran and Akyildiz, 2010, Bi et al., 2015).

RF energy harvesting can provide energy-on-demand by broadcasting radio waves to the sensor network when the sensors require to be energized to perform operations. However, the amount of the energy harnessed from radio waves is very low, which presents a significant impediment in the duty cycle and tasks accomplishment. The authors in (Seah and Olds, 2013) presented a sink synchronised data delivery protocol that aims to optimise the usage of the minute amounts of harvested RF energy. Active RF energy harvesting is when an RF energy transmitter (ET)

transmits energy to the WSN nodes using RF waves. The authors aim to lower the power requirements of the nodes to a minimum level. For this, a sink-synchronised polling method has been deployed in which the sink sends command to the nodes to perform operations at specific times. Before sending these directives the nodes, the sink will activate the ET to "send" power to the nodes. The proposed protocol was implemented on a custom-built sensor node platform. The authors adopted an experimental validation approach to model the actual environmental conditions experienced by energy harvesting systems.

WSNs using energy harvesters with supercapacitors, can operate perpetually until hardware failure and are deployed in places where it is difficult or impossible to replace batteries. In (Eu et al., 2011), authors analyze the performance of various MAC protocols based on collision sense multiple access (CSMA) and polling techniques for WSNs, which are powered by ambient energy harvesting. The authors also designed a probabilistic polling protocol that takes into account unpredictable nature of the energy harvesting process to enhance performance. To coordinate the transmission of each energy harvesting WSN node and to achieve timely and fair monitoring, appropriate MAC is needed. The major issue to be addressed is the time taken to charge the energy buffer of a node to an operational level, which varies due to ambient conditions and the type and form factor of the energy harvesters being used. The authors' analysis of different MAC performances focuses on network throughput (the rate at which the data is sent from all the sensor nodes to the sink), fairness (determines if each node is allocated an equal share of available spectrum or not) and inter-arrival time (the average time delay between the arrival of two consecutive packets at the sink from the same source). The analysis was performed for slotted CSMA, unslotted CSMA and ID polling. In slotted CSMA, a node can take one of the three states, which are charging, carrier sensing and transmit states. In the charging state, the processor and transceiver of the node are powered down to accumulate energy. The processor is active in the carrier sensing (transmit) state, and the transceiver is in

receive (transmit) mode. For unslotted CSMA, there are five states in which a sensor node could be viz. charging, carrier sensing, receive, idle and transmit states. In polling each sensor nodes is assigned a unique ID and is used as a standard MAC protocol for single-hop wireless networks comprising a sink and sensor nodes. The sink transmits a polling packet bearing the ID of the sensor to be polled, and on receiving the packet the sensor responds with packet transmission. The sink can determine the polling ID based on a predictable schedule by anticipating the state of the sensor. However, the energy charging times are uncertain and fluctuate in both time and space. If the polled sensor is receiving, it will send its sensed data back to the sink once receiving the polling packet. However, it is likely that it will not be polled again in the next round since it will be charging, and as a result the sink will be unable to get a response. Probabilistic polling protocol addresses the drawbacks of ID polling by adapting to the energy harvesting rates and/or the number of nodes in energy harvesting WSN. In probabilistic polling the sink sets a contention probability in the polling packet indicating the probability that a sensor should transmit its data packet instead of allocating unique ID to sensors. In probabilistic polling, only one out of all the sensors in the receiving state transmits its data packet when polled. QualNet network simulator was used to evaluate the performance of the various MAC protocols. The evaluation results showed that probabilistic polling gave high throughput and fairness while having low inter-arrival times and therefore is suitable to be used in energy harvesting WSN.

One of the problems of the RF energy transfer method is the significant variation in the energy harvesting rates of the individual sensors due their positions. The authors in (Jaeho and Jang-Won, 2011) propose a MAC protocol for WSNs based on RF energy transfer, called energy adaptive MAC (EA-MAC). The proposed MAC protocol considers amount of harvested energy and the contention time of sensor nodes to adaptively manage the duty cycle of sensor nodes at the same time maintaining fairness among them. The MAC protocols for the battery-powered

WSN can be classified into two categories, viz. synchronous and asynchronous. The synchronous approach synchronises neighbouring nodes in order to match their active or sleep schedule. Though this approach reduces listening time, however, it is not practical for RF energy transfer WSN due to synchronisation differences in the amount of energy harvested among nodes since a wake-up timer not able to work properly once energy is exhausted. On the other hand, asynchronous MAC schemes support low power consumption but require extra overheads on the sender side, in the form of preamble or extra beacon transmission. In the paper (Jaeho and Jang-Won, 2011), an RF energy transfer WSN is considered in a star topology that consists of a single master node capable of gathering data and slave nodes that can sense data and transmitting it to the master node. The master node operates using main power and transfers RF energy to the slave nodes, which they harvest to perform their operations. EA-MAC uses adaptive duty cycle management. The remaining energy level in each slave node's energy buffer is utilized to adjust the duty cycle of the slave nodes according to its harvested energy level. The authors used the OPNET simulator to evaluate the performance of the proposed EA-MAC. Their simulation result showed that EA-MAC with an energy adaptive contention algorithm could improve fairness compared to EA-MAC without the energy adaptive contention algorithm.

The authors in (Fafoutis and Dragoni, 2011) present ODMAC, an on-demand MAC protocol for energy harvesting WSNs which is able to assign individual duty cycles for nodes with varying energy profiles. ODMAC utilizes the carrier sensing technique to support individual duty cycles. Additionally, it also minimises energy wastage as the nodes are equipped with idle listening feature. The proposed protocol supports two operating modes, which are the static and the dynamic duty cycle mode. The administrator sets the sensing period and the beacon periods of each node in static mode, whereas in dynamic mode, the protocol periodically adjusts two duty cycles to reach the energy neutral operation (ENO) state. The major problem

of ODMAC is that the transmitter will have to wait for a long time if a receiver is on a high duty cycle period, which causes energy wastage and increase in the end-to-end packets delay. This problem has been addressed by integrating an opportunistic forwarding technique. ODMAC was tested using the OPNET simulator, which showed how the protocol optimizes the sensors performance in terms of their sensing rate and packet delay to adjust the energy consumption to a sustainable level maximizing the performance.

The paper (Iannello et al., 2012) addressed the analysis and design of energy harvesting WSNs by focusing on traditional MAC protocols – time division multiple access (TDMA), framed-ALOHA (FA) and dynamic-FA (DFA), and by considering trade-offs in performance and energy harvesting specific design issues. To address the analysis and design of medium access control (MAC) protocols for single-hop WSNs, the authors focused on system-level considerations for energy harvesting devices. A fusion centre (FC) collects data from sensors in its surroundings. The paper addressed the issues in the design of MAC protocols for single-hop WSNs with energy harvesting devices compared to battery-powered nodes by studying the trade-off between the delivery probability, which gives the measure of the capability of a MAC protocol to deliver the measured entity from a sensor to the targeted destination and the time efficiency, which is the FC's data collection rate. Novel design issues such as backlog estimation and frame length selection are also discussed.

As a trade-off is required between energy transfer and communication functions for appropriately sharing the channel this demands a novel perspective on medium access control (MAC) protocol design. Authors in (Naderi et al., 2014) have shown the effect on the sensor charging time due to the sensor's location, frequency used and the number of RF energy transmitters. The results of the studies are then used to design a MAC protocol called RF-MAC, which optimises energy delivery to sensor nodes with minimum disruption to data

communication. The work also encompasses designing a CSMA/CA based MAC protocol for in-band energy harvesting, in which data and energy are transferred using the same spectrum band. The authors experimentally identified the RF energy transferring MAC protocols' operating constraints and demonstrated how two slightly separated energy transfer frequencies could be assigned to energy transmitters (ETs) to improve constructive interference of their collective action. The authors evaluated the performance of the designed protocol using the NS-2 network simulator and conducted an experimental test-bed study by implementing the RF-MAC protocol in Mica2 motes. The simulation and test-bed results revealed that RF-MAC vastly outperforms the modified CSMA in both average harvested energy and average network throughput.

In (Nintanavongsa et al., 2013), the authors proposed two types of cross-layer protocols, namely device-agnostic (DA) and device-specific (DS), for energy harvesting sensor networks. The protocols evaluate the duty cycle (for both harvesting and transmission) and the routing paths at each hop for various conditions. DA protocol does not depend on the type and properties of the harvesting module. In addition, the optimal route and duty cycle are adapted for the source to destination nodes in WSN with entirely non-overlapping routes. On the other hand, in DS protocol there is no restriction in route formation. A single network-wide schedule is created, which make it possible for each node to transmit and recharge with exact synchronisation. However, it requires characterisation and knowledge of harvesting circuits, received power value and other parameters obtained through measurements or manufacturer's specifications. The authors evaluated the proposed protocol using an NS-2 network simulator and through experimental test-bed set up using Mica2 sensor motes. The evaluation result showed that the duty cycle of the DS protocol is much higher as compared to DA protocol. Also, DS scheme is preferred over DA scheme for applications where throughput is of utmost concern.

2.5 Use of Energy Prediction in Energy Management

The amount of RF energy harvested greatly depends upon the time, position and orientation of the nodes. Uncertain availability of ambient RF energy poses a challenge for developing an energy-efficient power management system (Cammarano et al., 2012).

The main issues that need to be addressed for maximizing energy efficiency for RF powered sensor nodes are:

1. Minimising energy waste, when the ambient RF energy is sufficient and the capacity limit of the energy storage devices is reached, the power management system should use the harvested energy to execute tasks such as sensing, processing and transmitting.
2. When there is a lack of available energy or energy harvesting is minimum, the sensor nodes still have to carry out tasks to maintain a minimum quality of service (Bergonzini et al., 2009).
3. The amount of harvested energy changes with time and RF frequency. There can be cases when more RF signals are available in a certain period than others. Likewise, signals with one frequency can have higher transmission power than others.

The issues can be handled properly if the future energy availability can be predicted and the system's energy utilisation is optimised according to the behaviour of the energy sources over short and medium time frames. Knowing available energy in the near future, the nodes can plan how to spend the energy they harvest and the energy available in the system. This will ensure exploiting at best the available energy, minimising the likelihood that essential tasks are not executed due to lack of energy and decreasing energy waste in cases where the harvested energy is neither used nor stored (Cammarano et al., 2012).

Table 2.4 Energy Management Technique Comparison for Harvesting Systems

Literature	Energy Management Technique	Performance
Kansal et al., 2007	EWMA based duty cycling	Energy efficiency comparable to theoretical optimal
Piorno et al., 2009	WCMA based duty cycling	Prediction error decreased to 10% from 90% (as compared to EWMA)
Cammarano et al., 2012	Pro-Energy (modified WCMA)	Prediction accuracy 60% higher than EWMA and WCMA
Aoudia et al., 2016	Fuzzy logic based duty cycling	Up to 25% more energy efficient than non-fuzzy based duty cycling energy management
Rodway and Musilek, 2017	Fuzzy logic based duty cycling	Improved performance compared to human-created reference controller
Qi et al., 2019	Rule based adaptive energy management	Extended lifetime

As sensor nodes can only accommodate limited computation, a low-cost energy prediction algorithm is normally implemented in sensor nodes. One of the widely used prediction algorithms is Exponentially Weighted Moving-Average (EWMA). EWMA gives the value of the energy likely to be harvested at a certain instance as a weighted average of the energy received at the same time over set of past days. Other existing works include the Weather-Conditioned Moving Average (WCMA). WCMA has its foundations on EWMA for the prediction of future energy availability but is different from the latter in that it not only takes into account the solar conditions at a particular time of day but also adjusts the harvested energy prediction for the changing weather conditions throughout a day (Piorno et al., 2009). Pro-Energy (Cammarano et al., 2012) is another prediction model that forecasts future harvested energy intake for short-term and medium-term predictions using the harvested energy information collected by the nodes. The model works in a way that it selects among the stored energy profiles of the past days, the one that is the most similar to the current day and provides future predictions. Other prediction models have also been proposed based on machine learning techniques and fuzzy systems (Piorno et al., 2009, Zhu et al., 2012, Azmat et al., 2016). Table

2.4 presents the comparison among various energy management techniques designed for energy harvesting system.

The authors in (Kansal and Srivastava, 2003) present an energy harvesting framework for sensor networks that adaptively learns the energy properties of the environment and gives localized algorithms to use the information in tasks such as load balancing, leader elections and energy aware communication. The framework is designed to predict the future availability of the amount of energy based on the availability of energy at present time. The prediction is carried by using prediction filters based on autoregressive methods. The authors compared the performance of the proposed framework with a residual energy based scheme, for routing and showed an improvement up to 200% in the lifetime of the sensor network.

A power management technique is presented in (Kansal et al., 2007) based on energy neutrality and energy storage requirements. The authors developed distributed methods to efficiently use harvested energy and characterise the complex time-varying nature of energy sources, particularly solar energy. They used a prediction model based on an exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA) filter, which uses the diurnal cycle in solar energy and also adapts to the variations in season. The authors have also proposed an energy-neutral and adaptive duty cycling algorithm based on future energy availability. The methods were implemented using the Heliomote platform to estimate the optimal performance in an energy-neutral mode. The result showed significantly higher performance levels than the existing works and was comparable to the theoretical optimal calculated using future estimate.

The work in (Bergonzini et al., 2009) presents a comprehensive comparison of various solar energy prediction algorithms, which give estimates of future energy availability. The performance among the predictors is based on memory requirements, time for prediction and average prediction error. The comparison was made among commonly used prediction

algorithms, which include weather conditioned moving average (WCMA), exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA), a predictor developed at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology of Zurich (ETHZ) and predictor based on neural network. It was found that EWMA and ETHZ occupied the least memory while EWMA took minimum time for prediction and the average prediction error was the least in the case of WCMA.

A prediction algorithm based on weather condition is described in (Piorno et al., 2009) for solar-based energy harvesting. The proposed weather-conditioned moving average (WCMA) prediction algorithm is based on an exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA). WCMA is different from EWMA in a way that the former also includes seasonal variations such as changes in the hour of sunrise and sunset and differences in solar intensity. The performance of WCMA was assessed using an energy harvesting wireless sensor node in the Shimmer platform, which uses a supercapacitor for energy storage and a solar panel for energy harvesting. The assessment showed a reduction in prediction error as low as 10% compared to EWMA.

In (Moser et al., 2010), the authors present a model based on predicting the future available energy for optimising problems related to buffer sizes, timing, and rates by adapting parameters of a solar-powered wireless sensor network. The proposed model incorporates linear programming for capturing the performance, parameters and energy model of energy harvesting systems. The upper control layer of the model designed considering worst-case prevents the sensor node from running out of energy. In contrast, the lower layer is responsible for the power-saving operation. The authors implemented the model experimentally and found the performance near to optimal solution.

A prediction model, termed as Pro-Energy, developed for solar and wind energy harvesting WSNs has been described in (Cammarano et al., 2012). The model comprises three

components: prediction module, profile analyser, and profile pool refresh, which can make short-term and medium-term energy predictions. The model tries to match the current day observations with one of the profiles stored in its pool for short-term predictions. The predicted value for the next timeslot is based on combining the next timeslot stored in the pool and the energy harvested in the last timeslot. On the other hand, the medium-term energy prediction is made by observing the correlation for relatively longer duration timeslots. The stored profiles are also updated periodically to discard obsolete and redundant profiles. The authors evaluated the predictor's performance using real-life datasets for harvested energy obtained using Telos B motes with photovoltaic cells and wind turbines for solar and wind, respectively. The results showed that Pro-Energy prediction accuracy is high as 60% compared to EWMA and WCMA.

A prediction model for wind farm power generation based on fuzzy modelling is presented in (Zhu et al., 2012). The authors propose a data-driven fuzzy model, which would forecast the wind power generated by a wind turbine. The model test showed a better prediction performance than other models, especially for short duration predictions (less than 0.5 hour).

The work presented in (Azmat et al., 2016) describes a prediction model of RF energy for wireless powered communications. The authors propose two models based on machine learning techniques, one using linear regression (LR) and the other using decision trees (DT). Frequency bands from 880 to 915 MHz and two types of harvesters having low and medium harvesting efficiencies were used to test and observe the models' performance. The results showed that the model based on LR has higher prediction accuracy than DT. However, the computation time required by LR was found to be more than DT. On further comparing the LR model with the moving average (MA) prediction model, the authors found the error to be smaller in LR than MA.

The work presented in (Jushi et al., 2016) proposes a network architecture for power management in wind energy harvesting systems for wireless sensor networks (WSNs), based on future energy prediction. The technique uses weather forecasts from the internet to make predictions and deploy power management policies ensuring autonomous operation of WSNs. The technique utilized for prediction is similar to exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA), except the weighing coefficients are adapted dynamically per past energy observations and future energy forecast. Three different power management policies have been devised considering energy neutral operation (ENO) and energy storage capacity and are implemented with a dynamic period adaptation. The duty cycling (wake-up and sleep period) is adjusted according to the stored charge level, predicted, harvested and consumed energy.

2.6 Summary and Research Gap

This chapter reviews literature related to energy harvesting technologies and the management of the harvested energy in sensor networks. Research on energy management issues such as data delivery, MAC and routing protocols, energy storage and transfer, hardware requirements, and duty cycling are also discussed. Works related to energy prediction techniques and energy prediction based energy management systems are also presented.

In the past works, many researchers have proposed different models for energy harvesting networks. The purpose of the model is to provide a generic architecture of an energy harvesting system that would incorporate all the parameters and functionalities related to the harvesting unit, power management (along with energy storage) unit and the application unit. RF energy harvesting systems differ from other energy harvesting types. The amount of harvested energy depends on the parameters like source-harvester separation, RF frequency, signal interference,

and the surrounding conditions (Zahid Kausar et al., 2014, Lu et al., 2015a). All these factors need to be considered while developing an RF energy harvester system model.

For RF energy harvester, the amount of harvested energy is relatively small. It often requires an energy storage element to reach a minimum level of energy before supplying to the application. The power management unit plays a crucial role in ensuring energy neutrality while maintaining equal energy distribution among nodes. Duty cycling is a widely used power management technique, where the nodes' 'sleep' and 'active' periods are set to maintain ENO and balance the energy levels among various nodes. The decisions made by the power management unit heavily relies on information regarding harvested energy level, remaining energy in buffer and application energy requirements.

Energy prediction is essential in knowing the amount of energy likely to be harvested in the future. The pre-knowledge of the energy availability helps to manage and adjust various network parameters in advance to avoid any worst-case scenarios and ensure optimal network performance. Different energy prediction techniques have been proposed and being researched for energy harvesting systems. Many of the techniques use past energy profiles and weather forecasts (in the case of solar and wind energy harvesting) along with fuzzy logic algorithms and machine learning tools for modelling and future energy predictions (Rodway and Musilek, 2017, Cammarano et al., 2016) . Prediction models are often coupled with power management policies incorporating load balancing, clustering techniques, routing and medium access algorithms.

It is observed from the review that many researchers have presented different models for energy harvesting networks based on solar energy, wind energy, vibration/kinetic energy and others. However, RF energy harvesting systems differ from other energy harvesting types such that the amount of harvested energy is dependent on the parameters like source-harvester

separation, RF frequency, signal interference and the surrounding conditions (Visser and Vullers, 2013). This work attempts to accommodate these parameters while developing the RF energy harvester model. Additionally, the model would also form a base for the development of RF energy prediction and energy management techniques.

Another aspect of the energy harvesting system is energy prediction, which is essential in knowing the amount of energy likely to be harvested in the future. Various energy prediction techniques have been proposed and being researched. These prediction models are often coupled with energy management policies to ensure optimal network performance. To devise an RF energy specific prediction model, it becomes necessary to exploit the characteristics of RF energy and then develop a prediction approach applicable for RF energy harvesting WSNs.

Finally, the energy management scheme plays a crucial role in ensuring energy neutrality while maintaining equal energy distribution among nodes. The network's lifetime needs to be prolonged without compromising information sensing and transmitting rates in addition to other network parameters. RF energy varies significantly within a short period compared to its wind and solar counterparts, so it becomes necessary to develop a prudent and robust energy management technique for RF powered WSNs, which can utilise stored charge level and energy forecast to implement adaptive energy management for individual sensor nodes.

Chapter 3

RF Energy Harvester Modelling

This chapter presents a model for RF-powered WSNs that uses available RF energy with variations in maximum and minimum energy levels for two different worst-case scenarios encompassing energy neutral operation (ENO) and buffer requirements. An algorithm based on the proposed model is developed to find each sensor node's optimum energy consumption rate that would ensure the maximum lifetime of the WSN with minimum buffer capacity. This approach has been verified by comparing the results with all other possible consumption rates. Moreover, a comparative analysis is performed to find available RF energy fluctuation's effect on the individual sensor nodes' lifetime.

3.1 Introduction

As discussed in previous chapters, RF energy harvesting has added benefits over other energy harvesting techniques. However, as a new element in WSNs, it also introduces challenges for developing efficient energy management systems and other design issues like data delivery scheme, topology, connectivity and energy storage technology (Lu et al., 2015a, Zahid Kausar et al., 2014). The research works discussed in Chapter 2 indicate that many researchers have proposed different energy harvesting networks based on solar energy, wind energy, vibration/kinetic energy, and others. However, RF energy harvesting systems differ from other energy harvesting types. The amount of harvested energy depends on the parameters like source-harvester separation, RF frequency, signal interference, and the surrounding conditions. These parameters are accommodated while developing the RF energy harvester model.

Figure 3.1 Block Diagram of an RF-EH System

For any EH system, to optimize energy utility and minimize waste, the system needs to operate following the source's energy profile, and its design should consider load and harvester properties (Pimentel and Musilek, 2010). Energy neutrality is a condition for an EH system to operate perpetually, i.e., for energy neutral operation (ENO), the energy used by a system should always be less than the energy harvested. ENO can be ensured by incorporating an

energy management system between the harvester and the load to satisfy the energy generation profile from the energy consumption profile (Zahid Kausar et al., 2014, Morsi et al., 2015) .

The energy management system can adopt two methods to control the incoming energy flow, i.e., harvest-use or harvest-store-use. In a harvest-use process, the harvested energy is immediately used to power the application. For this, the converted electricity has to exceed the minimum energy required by the application constantly. The network node has an energy storage buffer, a rechargeable battery, or a capacitor to store the converted electricity in the harvest-store-use method. Whenever the harvested energy is more than the load's consumption, the excess energy is stored in the buffer for future use (Lu et al., 2015a).

In determining the energy consumption rate for various associated source energy levels, it is necessary to develop a model for RF-powered WSNs to ensure continuous work of applications with minimal energy wastage even in worst-case scenarios. It should also apply to diverse ambient conditions. In addition, the relation between harvested energy, consumed energy and energy buffer size defined by the model should be able to represent the network's optimal performance scenario (Kansal et al., 2007).

Network lifetime is one of the crucial performance matrices for a WSN, which can be prolonged by improving its energy efficiency. Moreover, the location and orientation of sensor nodes affect their energy harvesting rates, which eventually determines the lifetime of each node. Understanding the relationship between the node's energy harvesting rate and lifetime, within the periphery of energy neutrality and zero energy wastage, is vital for designing any energy-aware routing algorithm (Cammarano et al., 2016, Mansourkiaie et al., 2017).

Figure 3.1 depicts a system model for RF powered WSN based on the harvest-store-use method that considers the worst-case scenarios. The model provides optimum load energy consumption rate and buffer size values for a given energy harvesting rate, increasing the WSN's lifetime.

3.2 Related Works

The work (Moser et al., 2010) propose a model for optimizing the energy management of sensor nodes powered by solar energy. The authors opted for offline multi-parametric programming to compute the application parameters and presented a software design comprising a worst-case prediction of the incoming energy. The authors evaluated the designed framework for the upper control layer, which prevents the sensor nodes from running out of power and the lower layer, ensuring minimal energy loss.

Another energy management framework based on solar energy harvesting has been proposed in (Castagnetti et al., 2012). The framework is used to simulate an energy harvesting sensor node based on power consumption and energy harvesting, considering energy-neutral and negative-energy conditions. The framework describes a generic energy harvesting system comprising charge consumption rate and energy availability as its parameters along with two energy management architectures: online duty-cycle adaptation and closed-loop power manager.

The definition of WSN lifetime differs depending on the type of application, primary function and topology of the network (Mansourkiaie et al., 2017). In some works (Chen et al., 2013, Najimi et al., 2014), network lifetime is specified as the instant at which a certain number of nodes run out of their stored energy. In (Salarian et al., 2014), the lifetime of the node consuming the highest power is considered as the network's lifetime, while the duration for which the first node in a network is depleted of energy is taken as the network's lifetime in (Jung and Weitnauer, 2013).

The work in (Mansourkiaie et al., 2017) presents a framework to maximize the lifetime of WSNs for structural health monitoring with and without energy harvesting. F. Mansourkiaie *et*

al. proposed an optimization technique for transmission power level and route selection for each sensor node based on *Branch-and-Bound* and *Genetic Algorithms*. The authors also compared their algorithm with the existing routing algorithms.

In (Akbas et al., 2016), the authors describe a joint optimization framework for transmission power level and packet size to maximize WSN lifetime. The work highlights the collective impact of the packet size and transmission power levels on the network lifetime. Also, it suggests an optimal packet size for each specific scenario where the network lifetime is higher than other packet sizes.

A. Kansal *et al* in (Kansal et al., 2007) present an EH system model based on ENO. The authors also incorporated energy storage parameters in the model and evaluated the experimental results with the theoretical optimal values. Solar-powered systems utilizing conservative duty cycle were used to compare the performance of the designed system with other approaches.

3.3 RF Energy Harvester Model

In (Kansal et al., 2007), the authors present an EH system model based on ENO. Energy source output power $P_s(t)$ and consumed power $P_c(t)$ at time t are defined using the same mathematical model. The conditions are presented below, which guarantees energy neutrality. The excess energy is stored in a storage device of capacity B . B_0 is considered as the initial stored energy, η the storage device charging efficiency (always less than 1) and P_{leak} the leakage loss. If $[x]^+$ is defined as a rectifier function such that $[x]^+ = x$ for $x \geq 0$ and $[x]^+ = 0$ for $x < 0$, then using law of energy conservation gives:

$$B_0 + \eta \int_0^T [P_s(t) - P_c(t)]^+ dt - \int_0^T [P_c(t) - P_s(t)]^+ dt - \int_0^T P_{leak}(t) dt \geq 0 \quad (3.1)$$

$$B_0 + \eta \int_0^T [P_s(t) - P_c(t)]^+ dt - \int_0^T [P_c(t) - P_s(t)]^+ dt - \int_0^T P_{leak}(t) dt \leq B \quad (3.2)$$

Equation (3.1) represents a sufficient and necessary condition to maintain ENO for all allowable $P_s(t)$ and $P_c(t)$. Equation (3.2) becomes necessary to make sure that energy is not wasted. For any energy harvester it is essential that it harvests enough energy to perform the assigned tasks, which the first condition implies. Second condition is for the cases when the amount of harvested energy exceeds the consumed energy and it becomes essential to store it for future use.

In the case of RF-EH, the associated power with the harvester reduces as the separation between the source and harvester increases. This is attributed to the path-loss, which is dependent on source-harvester distance, source frequency and the ambient conditions (Visser and Vullers, 2013). So, it becomes necessary to consider the path-loss or attenuation in the power level for an RF-EH system modelling. Implementation of RF-EH systems can vary from a scenario like free space (outdoor) to inside buildings (indoor) (Lu et al., 2015a). As such, various RF propagation models need to be considered depending on the location-based implementation. For source-harvester in free space, the propagation is described by the Friis transmission equation (Visser and Vullers, 2013)

$$P_R = P_T \frac{G_T G_R \lambda^2}{(4\pi r)^2} \quad (3.3)$$

Where P_R is the received power, P_T is the transmitted power, G_T is the transmit antenna gain, G_R is the receive antenna gain, λ is the signal wavelength, and r is the transmitter-receiver separation.

The indoor radio path-loss is characterized by both an average loss and its associated shadow fading statistics. International telecommunication union (ITU) site-general model for path loss prediction accounts for the loss through multiple floors to allow for such characteristics as

frequency reuse between floors. The model given below also includes an implicit allowance for transmission and loss mechanism within a single floor of a building (WP3K, 1999).

$$L_{total} = 20\log_{10}(f) + N\log_{10}(d) + Lf(n) - 28 \text{ dB} \quad (3.4)$$

Where N is the distance power decay index, f is the frequency in MHz, d is the distance in meters ($d > 1\text{m}$), $Lf(n)$ is the floor penetration loss factor, and n is the number of floors between the transmitter and receiver.

Based on the EH system model described in (Kansal et al., 2007) and represented by Equations (3.1) and (3.2), a system model is developed for RF powered WSNs encompassing ENO and buffer requirements. The model assumes average source energy emission and load energy consumption rate to be P_S and P_L , respectively. In addition, the model considers two worst case scenarios- first, the RF-EH system is consuming high amount of energy while the harvesting rate is low and second, the energy harvested is very high as compared to the consumption rate. To accommodate these cases, further assumption is made that the energy rates vary between two extremities: P_{Smax} and P_{Smin} for source emission, likewise P_{Lmax} and P_{Lmin} for load consumption, where the subscripts *max* and *min* represent maximum and minimum rates, respectively, such that

$$P_{Smax} = P_S + \sigma P_S \quad \text{and} \quad P_{Smin} = P_S - \sigma P_S \quad (3.5)$$

$$P_{Lmax} = P_L + \rho P_L \quad \text{and} \quad P_{Lmin} = P_L - \rho P_L \quad (3.6)$$

Where, σ and ρ is the variation factors defined in the interval $0 \leq \sigma \leq 1$ and $0 \leq \rho \leq 1$.

So, assuming an ideal buffer with zero leakage loss and capacity B , the two worst-case conditions for a given time interval T can be states as:

$$B_0 + \eta_{int} A(d, f, x) P_{Smin} T - P_{Lmax} T \geq 0 \quad (3.7)$$

$$B_0 + \eta_{int} A(d, f, x) P_{Smax} T - P_{Lmin} T \leq B \quad (3.8)$$

where B_0 is the initial energy stored in the buffer, η_{int} is the overall harvester efficiency and $A(d, f, x)$ represents the path-loss dependent on source-harvester separation (d), source

frequency (f) and ambient condition (x). The former ensures energy neutrality for the above-stated needs while the latter accommodates the additional constraint to satisfy the energy buffer size.

Considering the limiting conditions and setting T so as to ensure ENO for worst case scenarios, we get,

$$\frac{\eta_{int} A(d, f, x) P_{Smax} - P_{Lmin}}{P_{Lmax} - \eta_{int} A(d, f, x) P_{Smin}} = \frac{B - B_0}{B_0} \quad (3.9)$$

Equation (3.9) gives the optimum load consumption rate for any given P_S , considering the buffer capacity is always greater or at worst equal to the initial stored energy, i.e. $B \geq B_0$. This leads to,

$$R = \frac{B - B_0}{B_0} \geq 0 \quad (3.10)$$

Where R can be defined as buffer ratio, which gives the measure of buffer capacity.

The optimum values of P_{Lmax} and P_{Lmin} can be calculated for the given parameters as shown in Algorithm 3.1. The algorithm opts for the values from a possible set of energy consumption rates to best satisfy both conditions stated in Equations (3.7) and (3.8). The optimum average energy consumption rate and buffer ratio can be further deduced using the algorithm outputs.

Algorithm 3.1 Optimum Values for P_{Lmax} and P_{Lmin}

```

Input:  $P_{Smax}, P_{Smin}, \eta_{int}, A(d,f,x)$ 
Output: Optimum values for  $P_{Lmax}$  and  $P_{Lmin}$ 

 $P_{Lmax} = 0$ 
 $k = 0$ 
while  $P_{Lmax} \leq \eta_{int} A(d,f,x) P_{Smax}$ 
  for  $P_{Lmin} = 0$  to  $P_{Lmax}$ 
    if  $\frac{\eta_{int} A(d,f,x) P_{Smax} - P_{Lmin}}{P_{Lmax} - \eta_{int} A(d,f,x) P_{Smin}} \geq 0$ 
       $P_{L\_minimum}(k) = P_{Lmin}$ 
       $P_{L\_maximum}(k) = P_{Lmax}$ 
      increment  $k$ 
    end if
  end for
  increment  $P_{Lmax}$ 
end while
 $P_{L\_small} =$  smallest element among  $P_{L\_maximum}(k)$ 
 $P_{L\_large} =$  largest element among  $P_{L\_minimum}(k)$ 
for  $i = 0$  to  $k$ 
   $D\_max(i) = P_{L\_maximum}(i) - P_{L\_small}$ 
   $D\_min(i) = P_{L\_minimum}(i) - P_{L\_large}$ 
   $D\_sum(i) = D\_max(i) + D\_min(i)$ 
end for
 $ind =$  index of smallest element among  $D\_sum(i)$ 
 $P_{Lmax\_opt} = P_{L\_maximum}(ind)$ 
 $P_{Lmin\_opt} = P_{L\_minimum}(ind)$ 

```

3.4 RF Energy Harvester Simulation

This section analyses the optimum energy consumption rates for various source powers and the corresponding buffer ratios. The simulations are based on the proposed system model described in Section 3.3, which incorporates energy neutrality and buffer conditions. As the harvester efficiency does not vary significantly for a slight variation in the associated source power (Chaour et al., 2017, Visser and Vullers, 2013), for simulations, it is considered to be constant within the range of parameters used.

The simulation is performed in two stages. The first stage computes optimum energy consumption rate and buffer ratio for a given harvesting rate. Algorithm 3.1 is implemented using MATLAB, and P_S is varied to obtain the corresponding values of optimum P_L . Further, Equations (3.9) and (3.10) are utilized to evaluate R values. The second stage of the simulation incorporates network implementation of the obtained results using NS-2.35 simulator. Network lifetime of nodes with optimum consumption rate was compared against other non-optimal values. Likewise, similar analysis was carried out for the buffer capacity.

3.4.1 Results and Discussion

Table 3.1 MATLAB Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
Source to RF-EH distance	5 m
Source frequency	2.45 GHz
Overall harvester efficiency	0.7
Ambient condition	Free space

For simulations, the harvester efficiency is considered to be constant within the range of parameters used. The simulation parameters are listed in Table 3.1.

Figures 3.2 to 3.4 show the variation of average energy consumption rate (P_L) and buffer ratio (R) with available source power (P_S) for different values of variation factor (σ). The simulations show that for a constant value of σ , P_L increases with the increase in P_S , and as σ is increased, P_L tends to increase for same P_S values.

It is also evident from the results that the maximum value of R decreases for higher values of σ , suggesting a need for lower buffer capacity for high variations in source energy rate.

Figure 3.2 Optimal Energy Consumption Rate and Buffer Ratio for Variation of 0.1

Figure 3.3 Optimal Energy Consumption Rate and Buffer Ratio for Variation of 0.5

Figure 3.4 Optimal Energy Consumption Rate and Buffer Ratio for Variation of 0.9

The observations also show that as P_s increases, R decreases, increases or remains unchanged for different rates of change of P_L with P_s . It can be seen that R decreased for higher rates while remaining unchanged for intermediate values and increased for relatively lower rates.

Figure 3.5 Optimal Energy Consumption Rate Variation with Source-Harvester Separation Distance

Figure 3.6 Buffer Ratio Variation with Source-Harvester Separation Distance

Figures 3.5 and 3.6 show the variation of P_L and R with the separation distance (d) between the source and harvester for free space and indoor conditions. For simulation, P_S and σ were fixed to 2W and 0.1, respectively. As described in (WP3K, 1999), the ITU propagation model was used to calculate the path-loss for indoor conditions. It can be observed that P_L reduced significantly for indoor conditions, for the same values of d . This is attributed to the higher value of path-loss in indoor conditions. Similarly, the average value of R remained low for indoor than free-space.

The other objective of this work is to evaluate the WSN's lifetime (t_N) for the optimum energy consumption rate obtained from the MATLAB simulations. The measure for t_N is evaluated for a time window T , during which the average source energy rate is assumed to be $P_S (= 1W)$ with $\sigma (= 0.1)$ as the associated variation factor. To show that the obtained optimum consumption rate provides maximum network's lifetime with minimal buffer capacity, the network lifetimes and buffer capacities are compared with all the possible consumptions rates (P_L) obtained using Algorithm 3.1. For this, the network's lifetime is taken as the duration for which the first node of a WSN depletes its energy. A multi-hop WSN scenario in NS-2.35 is considered with

parameters as shown in Table 3.2. Thereafter, the network’s lifetime is analyzed for different energy consumption rates.

Table 3.2 NS-2.35 Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
Channel Type	Wireless
Propagation Model	Two-Ray Ground
MAC Type	802.11
Antenna Type	Omnidirectional
Routing Protocol	DSDV
Traffic	TCP (FTP)
Number of Nodes	5
Simulation Time	100s

Figure 3.7 Network Lifetime for Different Values of Energy Consumption Rates

Figure 3.8 Buffer Capacity for Different Values of Energy Consumption Rates

Figure 3.9 Lifetimes of Sensor Nodes with Optimal Energy Consumption Rate

Figures 3.7 and 3.8 depict the network lifetime and buffer capacity, respectively, for different values of load energy consumption rate. It is evident from the figure that the WSN lifetime, as compared to the optimum rate, is almost the same for lower consumption rates while dramatically shorter for higher rates. From the simulations, it was found that the increase in the lifetime was minimal for the lower values of consumption rate. Still, the corresponding buffer sizes were much larger, up to 180%, than the buffer size for the optimum energy consumption rate. On the other hand, though the buffer sizes for consumption rates higher than the optimum

rate are smaller by 50% to 90%, the network lifetime is significantly reduced by 95%. Hence, the observation indicates that a higher WSN lifetime can be achieved for a relatively lower value of buffer capacity.

The lifetimes of individual sensor nodes were analysed with optimum energy consumption rates for different values of the average source energy variation factor. Figure 3.9 illustrates that for minimum variation of 0.1, the maximum and minimum lifetimes are the same, however for higher variations the difference between maximum and minimum lifetimes tends to increase.

3.5 Summary

A model for RF powered WSN considering energy neutrality and minimum energy wastage is presented in this chapter. An algorithm is developed for optimal energy consumption rate and buffer capacity based on worst-case scenarios. Further, study was performed to analyse the changes in consumption rate and buffer capacity due to changes in source energy rate, ensuring continuous energy supply to the load and minimizing energy wastage. The effect of ambient conditions on consumption rate and buffer requirements was also observed.

The lifetime and buffer capacity of the WSN was also evaluated for optimum load energy consumption rate. We found that for the lower values of consumption rate, the increase in lifetime was minimal. Still, the corresponding buffer sizes were much larger, up to 180%, than the buffer size for the optimum energy consumption rate. On the other hand, though the buffer sizes for consumption rates higher than the optimum rate were smaller by 50% to 90%, the network lifetime was significantly reduced by 95%.

Chapter 4

Energy Prediction Model and Prediction Interval

This chapter presents a multi-node energy prediction method for radio frequency energy harvesting (RF-EH) WSNs, which predicts the future energy availability by considering the harvesting history of all nodes surrounding the central node. A mathematical model is developed to compute the optimum value of prediction interval, which significantly affects prediction accuracy and system design. Results show that multi-node prediction is less sensitive to prediction interval while inheriting the advantages of moving average (MA) techniques. Also, for prediction, nodes located at a larger distance were utilized less, and as the prediction interval increased, the utilization of more distant nodes decreased. Furthermore, the relationship between the prediction interval and the energy threshold limit was also studied.

4.1 Introduction

One of the aspects of the energy harvesting system is energy prediction, which is necessary to know the energy harvesting profile in advance so that the WSN's energy utilization is optimized based on the future energy availability (Bergonzini et al., 2009). Various energy prediction techniques have been proposed and being researched. These prediction models are often coupled with energy management policies to ensure optimal network performance. To devise an RF energy-specific prediction model, the characteristics of RF energy need to be exploited followed by formulation of a method applicable to RF energy harvesting sensor networks, which has been detailed in the following sections.

Figure 4.1 Multi-Node energy Prediction Model

Many works focused on environmentally powered systems (Kosunalp, 2017, Cammarano et al., 2016, Piorno et al., 2009) have incorporated various energy prediction models to ensure utilizing at best the available energy by minimizing the likelihood of inactive periods due to lack of energy and energy wastage during high harvesting rate (Cammarano et al., 2012). As RF energy suffers from reflection, diffraction, interference, scattering and others, its magnitude varies within small distances (Visser and Vullers, 2013). These characteristics have been

exploited in devising a multi-node energy prediction model for RF-EH WSNs. Figure 4.1 depicts the energy prediction model based on multiple nodes, where energy prediction for a node 'A' is made by considering the past energy profiles of that particular node and taking into account the harvesting history of its neighbouring nodes.

A novel energy prediction framework is devised, which is based on energy readings from multiple nodes for RF powered WSNs. The developed multi-node energy prediction technique predicts future energy availability for a node by utilizing past harvested energy readings from surrounding nodes. In addition, a model is presented to find the optimum prediction interval range for RF-EH sensor nodes adopting harvest-store-use mechanisms for power management.

4.2 Related Works

This section details the energy prediction approaches used for environmentally powered WSNs.

A prediction algorithm based on weather conditions is described in (Piorino et al., 2009) for solar-based energy harvesting. The proposed weather-conditioned moving average (WCMA) prediction algorithm is based on EWMA. WCMA differs from EWMA such that the former incorporates seasonal variations, which includes changes in the hour of sunrise and sunset and solar intensity differences. The evaluation for WCMA showed a reduction in prediction errors to as low as 10% compared to EWMA. Likewise, another prediction model, termed Pro-Energy, was developed for solar and wind energy harvesting WSNs (Cammarano et al., 2012). The model consists of three components—a prediction module, a profile analyser and a profile pool—and tries to match the current day's observations with one of the profiles stored in its

collection. The results demonstrated Pro-Energy prediction accuracies as high as 60% compared to EWMA and WCMA. Similarly, the work in (Bergonzini et al., 2009) presented a comprehensive comparison of various solar energy prediction algorithms. It was found from the comparisons that EWMA and the predictor developed at the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology of Zurich (ETHZ) occupied the least memory. At the same time, EWMA took the shortest time for prediction, with the average error in prediction being the smallest in the case of WCMA. These works, however, only present prediction models based on a single node and do not consider the harvesting history of the neighbouring nodes while forecasting future energy availability for a particular node.

There has been significant research in the area of prediction-based power management for EH networks. One such work is presented in (Kansal et al., 2007), where the authors developed distributed methods to use harvested energy efficiently. The authors propose an energy-neutral and adaptive duty cycling algorithm based on the EWMA energy prediction model. The result showed significantly higher performance levels, comparable to the theoretical optimal calculated using complete future knowledge. The authors in (Jushi et al., 2016) also proposed network architecture for energy management in the wind-powered WSNs, based on future energy prediction. The architecture uses a weather forecast from the internet for making predictions and deploying power management policies to ensure the autonomous operation of WSNs. The method used for prediction was similar to EWMA with adjustable weighting coefficients. The power management policy incorporates a dynamic period adaptation adjusted based on the state of the charge stored, predicted consumed and harvested energy. In (Moser et al., 2010), the authors presented a model based on predicting future available energy for optimizing problems related to buffer sizes, timing, and rates by adapting the parameters of a solar-powered WSN. The proposed model incorporates linear programming for capturing the performance, parameters, and energy model of energy harvesting systems.

4.3 Energy Prediction Model and Prediction Interval

Most energy forecasting methods are based on the Moving Average (MA) technique, which predicts the future value by taking an average of recent past values within a window of a certain length. In Simple Moving Average (SMA) model, a simple average of the most recent m values is taken such that each past observation gets a weight of $1/m$. Hence, as m gets larger, it will yield a smoother-looking series of forecasts but will lag in responding to trends and turning points. On the other hand, the Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA) model gives relatively more weight to the recent observations than the older values. For this, a weighting factor, $0 < \alpha < 1$, is used as exponentially decreasing weight on the past values to do a forecast (Prema and Rao, 2015, Nau, 2014).

4.3.1 Multi-Node Energy Prediction Model

Figure 4.2 Node 'A' with Neighbouring Nodes

Figure 4.3 Time Frame Showing Prediction Instances

Multi-node prediction model is based on the notion that there is significant variation in the magnitude of harvested RF energy even among the nodes lying within close vicinity. This phenomenon is due to the propagation characteristics of RF signal, and the degree of variation mainly depends on the frequency of the RF signal (Visser and Vullers, 2013). Figure 4.2 shows

nodes of an RF-EH sensor network, with *Node-A* surrounded by n number of nodes, namely *Node-1*, *Node-2*, *Node-3*, up to *Node-n*.

The RF energy harvested by *Node-A* at any time instance can be predicted using the harvesting history of *Node-A* and its surrounding nodes. Figure 4.3 shows the prediction time frame with τ as the time duration between two consecutive predictions (prediction interval) and t , $t+\tau$, $t+2\tau$ and so on as prediction instances. The theory behind the multi-node prediction method is that if the harvesting profile of neighbouring nodes for time t is known, it can be used to estimate the harvested energy for *Node-A* for that particular instance. The energy estimation for *Node-A* is carried out by assuming that all nodes hold location-based information, which is used to calculate the estimated energy using a suitable radio wave propagation model for any centre node (in this case *Node-A*) with respect to its neighbouring nodes. Using the estimated energy for *Node-A* corresponding to each neighbouring node, future energy availability is predicted for instance $t+\tau$. We will have $n+1$ different versions of predictions for *Node-A* for all prediction instances. Next, the node with the least prediction error is chosen as the reference node for prediction instance $t+2\tau$ and so on.

Algorithm 4.1 Multi-Node energy prediction algorithm

1. For time t , predict energies for Node-A - $\hat{e}_A(t)$, $\hat{e}_{1A}(t)$, $\hat{e}_{2A}(t)$, ..., $\hat{e}_{nA}(t)$ with respect to *Node-A*, *Node-1*, *Node-2*, ..., *Node-n*.
 2. Calculate prediction errors- ε_A , ε_{1A} , ε_{2A} , ..., ε_{nA} . Where $\varepsilon_A = \Delta(\text{Rodway and Musilek})$, $\varepsilon_{1A} = \Delta[e_A(t) - \hat{e}_{1A}(t)]$ and so on. Here, Δ is error function.
 3. Find the corresponding node i with least prediction error.
 4. Evaluate predicted energy for instance $t+\tau$, i.e, $\hat{e}_A(t+\tau) = \beta[e_{iA}(t), e_{iA}(t-1), e_{iA}(t-2), \dots, e_{iA}(t-m)]$. Here, β is prediction function.
 5. For time $t+\tau$, repeat 2 and so on.
-

In Step 4 of Algorithm 4.1, $e_{iA}(t)$, $e_{iA}(t-1)$, $e_{iA}(t-2)$, ..., $e_{iA}(t-m)$ represent estimated energies for *Node-A* with respect to one of its neighbouring nodes i having the least prediction error. The prediction function β , which can be any of the MA-based prediction techniques, is then used to predict the future energy $\hat{e}_A(t+\tau)$. For the next prediction cycle, prediction errors for *Node-A* are calculated as in Step 2 and the corresponding node giving the least error is selected for subsequent prediction and so on.

4.3.2 Optimum Energy Prediction Interval

The prediction accuracy depends on the prediction interval. As the prediction interval increases, the prediction error tends to decrease (discussed later in Section 4.4). Also, in harvest-store-use network architecture (Lu et al., 2015b), it is crucial to make an energy availability prediction before the stored energy in the buffer is too low to power the necessary scheduled task. These situations call for the prediction interval to be bounded within a range so that predictions can be made as quickly as possible with an acceptable prediction error. For this, the RF-EH model presented in Chapter 3 is utilized to develop a mathematical formulation for estimating an optimum prediction interval range that can accommodate the above situations.

Figure 4.4 Prediction Interval with Sleep and Active States

Figure 4.4 represents *Sleep* and *Active* states for a typical EH node (Kansal et al., 2007). During the *Sleep* state, an RF-EH node harvests energy from the source, stores it in the buffer and performs no tasks, i.e., during this state, a node ideally does not consume any energy. On the contrary, when the node is in the *Active* state, it performs the scheduled network operation alongside harvesting energy and storing it in the buffer.

If e_{sleep} is the energy stored in the buffer during the *Sleep* state, then

$$e_{sleep} = P_{savg} \cdot t_s \quad (4.1)$$

where P_{savg} and t_s represent the average RF energy harvesting rate and *Sleep* time, respectively.

Likewise, for an arbitrary interval of Δt_a during the *Active* period, the energy stored in the buffer can be represented by e_{sb} as,

$$e_{sb} = e_i + P_{savg} \cdot \Delta t_a - P_{Lavg} \cdot \Delta t_a \quad (4.2)$$

where e_i is the energy stored in the buffer at the beginning of Δt_a and P_{Lavg} is the average energy consumption rate when nodes are *Active*.

If an arbitrary interval is considered to always begin from the very start of the *Active* state, then $e_i = e_{sleep}$. This assumption is made to avoid the chances that a node runs out of its energy before a prediction is made. Also, replacing P_{Lavg} by the optimum energy consumption rate, P_{Lopt} as described in Chapter 3 ensures an optimal utilization of the harvested energy maximizing the RF-EH WSN lifetime. Then, Equation (4.2) can be rewritten as follows:

$$e_{sb} = e_{sleep} + P_{savg} \cdot \Delta t_a - P_{Lopt} \cdot \Delta t_a \quad (4.3)$$

To maintain energy neutrality, the energy consumed in Δt_a should always be less than or, at worst, equal to the sum of stored energy and harvested energy during the interval. That is,

$$P_{Lopt} \cdot \Delta t_a \leq P_{savg} \cdot \Delta t_a + e_{sb} \quad (4.4)$$

This leads to,

$$P_{savg} \cdot \Delta t_a + e_{sb} - P_{Lopt} \cdot \Delta t_a \geq 0 \quad (4.5)$$

To ensure that the energy prediction is made well before the limiting condition given by Equation (4.5), a threshold energy level $k \cdot e_{sleep}$ (where k is a threshold constant defined in the interval $[0,1]$) is introduced, such that for a prediction interval of τ the following condition is satisfied,

$$P_{savg} \cdot \tau + e_{sb} - P_{Lopt} \cdot \tau = k \cdot e_{sleep} \quad (4.6)$$

Further, from Equation (4.6) we can derive,

$$\frac{\tau}{t_s} = \frac{(k - 1)P_{savg}}{2(P_{savg} - P_{Lopt})} \quad (4.7)$$

Equation (4.7) provides a measure for the prediction interval τ based on an optimum energy consumption rate P_{Lopt} , which ensures energy neutrality and minimal energy wastage.

4.4 Energy Prediction Model Simulation

The simulation was carried out in the MATLAB (R2017b) platform. RF source with omni-directional antenna and sinusoidal impulse response were linked with the individual sensor nodes through an additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channel to mimic the effect of the random process. The AWGN channel model was chosen as it is best suited for static (non-mobile) energy harvesting sensor nodes (Veilleux et al., 2017). A mean of 0 ($\mu = 0$) and variance of 0.1 ($\sigma = 0.1$) were assumed for channel modelling. A free-space path loss model was incorporated throughout the simulation to estimate the energy loss during the signal propagation. An ideal lossless buffer was considered, and the overall harvester efficiency was set to be 0.7, which included the efficiencies of antenna, rectifier and converter circuits combined.

Figure 4.5 Simulation Layout-1 for Multi-Node Prediction

Table 4.1 Simulation Parameters

Source Power	60 W
Source Frequency	2.45 GHz
Harvester Efficiency	0.7
L	20 m
d₁	1 m
d₂	2.5 m
d₃	5 m
d₄	7 m

The layout-1 of the simulated network considering four neighbouring nodes is shown in Figure 4.5. *Node-A* is the node of interest for which energy prediction is to be made with *Node-1*, *Node-2*, *Node-3* and *Node-4* as neighbouring nodes at a distance of d_1 , d_2 , d_3 and d_4 , respectively. A single RF source at a distance L and with the specifications presented in Table

4.1 was considered for the simulation. For layout-1, the nodes were arranged such that the angle of separation between *Node-1/Node-2*, *Node-2/Node-3*, *Node-3/Node-4* and *Node-4/Node-1* were 60° , 40° , 20° and 240° , respectively, with *Node-A* being the centre node. Likewise, for layout-2, a star topology was formed with *Node-A* surrounded by eight nodes placed at 0.5 m, 2 m, 3.5 m, 4 m, 6 m, 8 m, 10 m and 12 m; with a 45° angle of separation between adjacent nodes.

Multi-node energy prediction algorithm was used to estimate the future energy availability for *Node-A*. For this, as discussed in Section 4.3, the estimated harvested energy for *Node-A* with respect to all the neighbouring nodes was used to compute the predicted energy values corresponding to each node (including *Node-A*). Multi-Node energy prediction algorithm was implemented using SMA ($m = 10$) as the prediction function in our simulation. The simulation was performed for varying prediction intervals. Table 4.2 shows the measurements of actual harvested energy along with predicted values for prediction intervals of 60s.

Table 4.2 Actual and Predicted Energy for Prediction Interval of 60s

Time Slots	Actual Harvested Energy (μJ)	Predicted Harvested Energy (μJ)			
		SMA	EWMA	Multi-Node (layout-1)	Multi-Node (layout-2)
15	2.71	3.07	2.87	3.07	3.07
25	2.71	2.91	2.71	2.67	2.78
35	3.17	2.55	2.80	2.55	2.55
45	3.09	2.75	2.80	2.75	2.77
55	2.86	2.91	2.91	2.84	2.78

Figures 4.6 and 4.7 depict the actual harvested energy by *Node-A* along with predicted energy using SMA ($m = 10$), EWMA ($\alpha = 0.4$) and the proposed multi-node prediction algorithm. From the figures, it can be observed that the EWMA prediction approach follows the actual energy profile better than SMA and multi-node. However, in terms of Mean Absolute

Percentage Error (MAPE), taken for an hour, SMA performed better compared to the other two. Similarly, Figures 4.8 and 4.9 show the actual and predicted energy for *Node-A* considering eight neighbouring nodes. It is evident from Table 4.3 that as the prediction interval decreases, the multi-node prediction approach gives better results than the other two approaches.

Figure 4.6 Actual and Predicted Energy for Prediction Interval of 60s (for layout-1)

Figure 4.7 Actual and Predicted Energy for Prediction Interval of 30s (for layout-1)

Figure 4.8 Actual and Predicted Energy for Prediction Interval of 60s (for layout-2)

Figure 4.9 Actual and Predicted Energy for Prediction Interval of 30s (for layout-2)

Table 4.3 MAPE Summary Table

Prediction Interval	MAP Error			
	SMA	EWMA	Multi-Node (layout-1)	Multi-Node (layout-2)
1sec	1282.32	1375.55	619.60	764.43
5 sec	48.70	53.66	49.54	51.07
10 sec	29.10	31.93	32.24	34.05
30 sec	15.88	17.87	17.83	22.82
60 sec	8.51	10.42	8.25	10.65

Observations were also made for node usage during multi-node energy prediction. The analysis was carried out to understand the extent of the effective distance to which a neighbouring node can be considered for prediction. The other reason for the observation was to understand the effect of the prediction interval on the effective distance. Figures 4.10 and 4.11 show the percentage usage of neighbouring nodes located at various distances from the node of interest for varied prediction intervals. Two significant phenomena were observed from the analysis. First, nodes located at a larger distance were utilized less for prediction compared to nearer neighbouring nodes. Second, as the prediction interval increased, the utilization of more distant nodes decreased, suggesting that the extent of the considered adjacent nodes was more extensive for smaller prediction intervals.

Figure 4.10 Neighbouring Node Usage Percentage for Different Prediction Intervals (for layout-1)

Figure 4.11 Neighbouring Node Usage Percentage for Different Prediction Intervals (for layout-2)

From Figure 4.12 and Table 4.3, it can be observed that prediction error decreased considerably for larger forecast durations. This implies that the prediction interval should be chosen so that the error is within acceptable limits. Also, the prediction should be made before the node energy falls below a threshold value, as discussed in Section 4.3. To find this optimum range of prediction interval, first, the optimum energy consumption rate P_{Lopt} was calculated using the method detailed in Chapter 3, which was finally used in Equation (4.7).

Figure 4.12 MAPE for Various Prediction Intervals (for layout-1)

The variation of the prediction interval with threshold constant k is presented in Figure 4.13. It can be observed that for longer prediction intervals, a relatively smaller prediction threshold is required. This points to the trade-off required between a nominal prediction error and the chances that a node runs out of energy before any prediction can be made. Based on this observation, the remaining energy in buffer (after a prediction is made) was also compared with the assumed threshold energy. Figure 4.14 presents the measurement of remaining energy for different values of prediction intervals observed for various threshold constant k . It can be seen that for greater values of k , the remaining energy is well above the threshold limit. On the other hand, for lower values of k , it is either marginal or below the assumed reference. The former is desirable as it would ensure sufficient energy in a node to carry out its operations.

However, larger values of k would lead to a smaller prediction interval that would eventually produce a more significant prediction error.

Figure 4.13 Prediction Intervals for Different Threshold Values

Figure 4.14 Variations of Remaining Energy and Threshold Energy against Prediction Interval for Various Values of Threshold Constant: (a) $k = 0.1$; (b) $k = 0.3$; (c) $k = 0.5$; (d) $k = 0.7$

4.5 Summary

In this chapter, a novel multi-node approach for predicting future energy availability for RF-powered WSNs was presented. To the best of found knowledge, no prior work has utilized energy readings from neighbouring nodes to make energy predictions. The prediction approach considers the harvesting history of all nodes surrounding the central node for which energy prediction is made. Once the predicted values corresponding to each node are calculated, they are matched with the actual harvested energy and the node giving the least error is taken as the reference node for the next prediction, and so on. In this way, the reference nodes are switched from one node to another for each prediction based on the prediction error.

The prediction results were compared with SMA (for window size 10) and EWMA (for weighing coefficient 0.4). Different values of prediction interval were considered, and MAPE was calculated for each prediction method. The results showed that EWMA followed the energy profile best, while the Multi-Node approach was between EWMA and SMA. In terms of prediction error, SMA had the lowest MAPE (except for a prediction interval of 1s for which multi-node showed the least error) for the considered prediction intervals, although it could be observed that the multi-node prediction method was less sensitive to prediction intervals than the other two. Overall, it can be said that the multi-node prediction approach combines the advantages of both SMA and EWMA, i.e., it follows the energy profile better with less prediction error. Analyses were also made to determine the effective distance up to which a neighbouring node can be considered for prediction and the effect of prediction interval on the effective distance. It was found that nodes located at larger distances were utilized less for prediction, and as the prediction interval increased, the utilization of farther nodes decreased.

A mathematical model was also developed to compute the optimum value of prediction interval, which is essential in designing power management systems for EH-WSNs. The

mathematical model was formulated for an RF-EH sensor node with an optimum energy consumption rate considering energy neutrality and minimum energy wastage. A linear relation was established between the prediction interval and the energy threshold (limit before a prediction should be made). The relation is crucial in determining an optimum prediction interval to ensure a satisfactory prediction accuracy and a timely prediction before a node runs out of its energy.

Chapter 5

FEMS: A Fuzzy-Based Adaptive Energy Management System

This chapter presents a fuzzy energy management system (FEMS) utilizing buffer charge level and harvested energy forecast to implement adaptive duty cycling for individual nodes. Low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) protocol is considered for FEMS's network implementation and its performance is compared with the rule-based approach. The proposed scheme, FEMS, adapts to the changes in buffer charge levels and harvested energy predictions, enabling the sensor node to dynamically adjust its duty cycling and sleep-active pattern for a robust operation. Results show that FEMS highly improves the network's lifetime and significantly reduces data loss compared to the rule-based approach. In addition, FEMS demands a smaller buffer capacity, aiding in reducing the size and cost of a sensor node.

5.1 Introduction

It was discussed in the previous chapters that energy management technique plays an essential role in ensuring energy neutrality while maintaining equal energy distribution among nodes for energy harvesting devices. The network's lifetime must be prolonged without compromising information sensing and transmitting rates and other network parameters. As RF energy varies significantly within a short period, it becomes crucial to develop a prudent and robust energy

Figure 5.1 Fuzzy-Based Energy Management System Model

management technique for RF powered WSNs. The aim is to design and evaluate an energy management system in this chapter, utilizing buffer charge level and harvested energy forecast to implement adaptive duty cycling for individual sensor nodes.

Various works on energy harvesting WSN based on wind and solar have adopted prediction based energy management techniques to optimize network's energy utilization. The pre-knowledge of energy availability helps manage and adjust network parameters in advance, ensuring optimal network performance (Baroudi, 2019, Cammarano et al., 2016). However, as RF energy varies significantly within a short period (Visser and Vullers, 2013), developing a prudent and robust energy management technique becomes crucial for RF-powered WSN.

Fuzzy logic helps conceptualize the fuzziness in a system into a crisp quantifiable parameter (Suganthi et al., 2015), so it is often used to design energy management units for harvesting systems, which are otherwise difficult to model (Rodway and Musilek, 2017).

Figure 5.1 depicts the proposed energy management system based on fuzzy logic for RF powered WSNs. The proposed fuzzy energy management system (FEMS) consists of a fuzzy inference system (FIS) (Azeem, 2012), which provides budget estimates with stored charge levels and energy forecast as inputs to implement adaptive duty cycling for individual nodes. Low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) protocol is adopted for network implementation and FEMS's network performance is evaluated in terms of dead nodes, data loss and network's lifetime.

5.2 Related Works

There have been many works done in the area of prediction-based energy management for energy harvesting systems. The authors in (Kansal et al., 2007) present an energy-neutral and adaptive duty cycling algorithm efficiently using harvested energy. The algorithm based on exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA) energy prediction model showed a higher performance level comparable to theoretical optimal. An adaptive energy management scheme for solar-powered WSN is described in (Moser et al., 2010). The model uses future energy availability to optimize problems related to buffer size, sleep-wake timing, and rates by incorporating linear programming for capturing the performance, parameter, and energy model of harvesting systems. In (Jushi et al., 2016) authors present an energy management architecture using weather forecast for making predictions and deploy energy management policy to ensure autonomous operation of wind-powered WSN. The approach uses a dynamic

period adaptation technique, adjusted based on stored charge level, harvested, and predicted consumed energy. Another energy control algorithm for energy prediction is discussed in (Zou et al., 2016), which uses environmental shadow detection. The solar-powered sensor nodes adjust their scheduling plans following the energy production and residual battery levels to improve the energy efficiency and prolong the network lifetime. The work in (Qi et al., 2019) proposes an adaptive energy management scheme for solar-powered WSNs. The authors have presented a rule-based energy management strategy, which is adaptive to the energy storage device capacity and the load conditions.

In recent times fuzzy-based energy management techniques have been widely adopted due to their ability to make real-time decisions, even with incomplete information. Fuzzy logic controllers (FLCs) are generally used to implement multi-criteria control strategies and combine different parameters and rules, which may produce optimum results. The authors in (Aoudia et al., 2016) propose a power management framework based on fuzzy control theory. They use a harvest-use (store) mechanism to handle the harvested solar energy. The framework computes the node's energy budget for the current time slot using FIS with inputs as residual energy and energy harvesting for the previous time slot. The work in (Rodway and Musilek, 2017) describes a harvesting-aware energy management system using FLC. The described system combines daily solar energies forecasts with FLC tuned using differential evolution to provide node-level energy management through adaptive duty cycling. The fuzzy logic controller showed improved performance as compared to the human-created reference controller. Another fuzzy logic-based energy management approach is presented in (Collotta et al., 2017) for battery-powered WSNs. The authors in (Collotta et al., 2017) propose a strategy to dynamically regulate the sleeping time of industrial wireless sensor networks (IWSNs) nodes by using an FLC to address the power consumption problem. The authors also utilize the particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm for optimizing FLC parameters.

5.3 Energy Management System Model

As shown in Figure 5.1, the system model utilizes a harvest-store-use mechanism, where a sensor node harvests energy from a nearby RF source(s), stores the energy in a buffer (rechargeable battery or super-capacitor) uses the stored energy to power the node. For simplicity, an ideal buffer of maximum capacity, B_{max} is considered. The energy management

Figure 5.2 Frame Structure with Active and Sleep States

system estimates the energy budget for the next time frame, considering the current buffer charge level and predicted harvested energy for the upcoming time frame. A duty cycle is established based on the allocated budget for the node (load) to operate accordingly.

A node enters in sleep state if its buffer charge level is less than the threshold energy $E_{threshold}$. The sleep state is assumed to be of fixed period T_{sleep} during which a node suspends all activities except harvesting energy from the source and storing it in the buffer. The active state comprises frames with a duration equal to the prediction interval. Energy prediction for the upcoming frame is made at the end of each frame. Further, for frame i the time-slots t_i are divided into equal duration as in Figure 5.2. For a certain amount of harvested energy $E_{harvest}$ and consumed energy E_{load} determined by the duty-cycle $D(t_i)$, the buffer charge level E_{buf} at the start of a time-slot can be numerically presented as:

$$E_{buf}(t_i + 1) = E_{buf}(t_i) - E_{load}(t_i) + E_{harvest}(t_i) \quad (5.1)$$

The buffer charge level at the end of frame k , $E_{buf}(t_k)$ and predicted harvested energy for frame $k+1$, $E_{predict}(t_{k+1})$ are fed as inputs to FEMS producing energy budget estimate $E_{bud}(t_{k+1})$, which is further utilized to calculate duty-cycle $D(t_k)$.

5.3.1 Rule-Based Scheme

Figure 5.3 Rule Based Scheme

The flowchart for rule-based scheme based on (Kansal et al., 2007, Qi et al., 2019) is shown in Figure 5.3. The strategy considered buffer charge level E_{buf} of RF powered sensor node and predicted energy $E_{predict}$ to determine the budget estimate E_{bud} for the upcoming frame. A node enters sleep state if its charge level depletes below $E_{threshold}$ and remains in the condition for T_{sleep} duration. An energy budget is estimated under the strategy, and subsequently, the duty-cycle is established. Thus obtained duty-cycle is adaptive; however, the method may not cover all the possible cases, especially for RF powered WSNs, where there is a rapid and sudden variation in harvested energy (Aoudia et al., 2016, Pau and Salerno, 2019). As a result, a less

fine-tuned budget is estimated, affecting the network's overall performance. To overcome this issue, a fuzzy-logic based energy management strategy is presented in the following section.

5.3.2 Fuzzy Energy Management System (FEMS)

The proposed FEMS considers two member functions (Low, High) for predicted harvested energy. For buffer charge level, three member functions (Minimum, Optimum, Maximum) are considered. The output energy budget consists of three member functions (Small, Medium, High). The inference rules are presented in Table 5.1. Figures 5.4 to 5.6 show the member functions for inputs and output. Trapezoidal member functions are assumed for predicted harvested energy, while a mix of trapezoidal and triangular member functions are chosen for buffer charge and energy budget.

Table 5.1 Inference Rules

Rule	Buffer Charge Level (Input 1)	Predicted Harvested Energy (Input 2)	Energy Budget (Output)
1	Minimum	Low	Small
2	Optimum	Low	Medium
3	Maximum	Low	Large
4	Minimum	High	Medium
5	Optimum	High	Large
6	Maximum	High	Large

Figure 5.4 Predicted Energy Member Functions

Figure 5.5 Buffer Charge Member Functions

Figure 5.6 Energy Budget Member Function

Figure 5.7 Surface Generation of the FIS

5.3.3 LEACH Protocol

Low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) protocol is chosen to implement the proposed FEMS. LEACH protocol is one of the widely used routing protocols for wireless sensor networks (WSNs) and boasts of being energy efficient, with its energy balancing clustering scheme. A WSN's lifetime is greatly influenced by the lifetime of individual sensor nodes. LEACH protocol plays a central role in distributing fair loads among the sensor nodes by random selection of cluster head (CH) in each round. In this mechanism, sensor nodes in a cluster transmit data to the base station through the cluster head (Singh et al., 2017, Mouapi et al., 2018). The LEACH protocol is adapted to evaluate the network performance so that the time spent on each round corresponds to the prediction interval or a single frame duration.

5.4 Energy Management System Simulation

To simulate the harvested RF energy, an RF energy source with an omni-directional antenna and sinusoidal impulse response is considered as described in Chapter 4. Free-space path loss model is used for estimating energy loss during signal propagation. To predict the harvested RF energy, exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA) technique is utilized. Maximum buffer capacity B_{max} and consumed energy E_{load} are calculated using guidelines in Chapter 3 to maintain energy neutral operation (ENO). Both T_{sleep} and frame duration are assumed to be thirty seconds, with one frame consisting of thirty time-slots.

5.4.1 FEMS Parameters

EB_{Max} is assumed as the product of average source power and T_{sleep} . EB_{Min} is taken to be 40% of EB_{Max} and the mean of two extremities EB_{Max} and EB_{Min} gives the measure for EB_{Opt} . Energy budget parameters are set considering ENO and minimum energy wastage. For this, the techniques described in (Kansal et al., 2007) and in Chapter 3 are adopted to calculate $EBud_{Large}$ such that it is equal to the product of the optimum load consumption rate and prediction interval (or frame duration). $EBud_{Small}$ is set to be 40% of $EBud_{Large}$, and $EBud_{Med}$ is the mean of the two extremes. Table 5.2 presents in detail the FEMS parameters with respective values and ranges.

Table 5.2 FEMS Parameters

Input/Output	Range	Parameter	Value
Predicted Harvested Energy	0 to 46 μJ	EH_{Low}	15.8 μJ
		EH_{High}	17.5 μJ
Buffer Charge Level	0 to 47.1 μJ	EB_{Min}	9.7 μJ
		EB_{Opt}	17.0 μJ
		EB_{Max}	24.2 μJ
Energy Budget	0 to 32.7 μJ	$EBud_{Small}$	13.1 μJ
		$EBud_{Med}$	22.9 μJ
		$EBud_{Large}$	32.7 μJ

5.4.2 Network Parameters

LEACH protocol is implemented to evaluate FEMS network performance. Table 5.3 presents the network parameters. The network deployment area varies with the number of sensor nodes n in the network. For $n=20$, the network area is set to be $20*20 m^2$; for $n=50$ the deployment area is $50*50 m^2$ and so on. Figure 5.8 shows the network implementation of the LEACH protocol for 200 nodes. Circles with a cross represent cluster head nodes connected (via blue lines) to other ordinary nodes in the cluster. Red circles represent dead nodes.

Table 5.3 WSN Parameters

Parameter	Value
Deployment areas	$20*20 m^2$, $50*50 m^2$, $100*100 m^2$, $200*200 m^2$
Number of nodes	20, 50, 100, 200
Data packet size	50 bytes
Energy dissipated in Tx/Rx	50 nJ/bit
Base station location	Outside WSN area
Nodes deployment	Random

Figure 5.8 Network Implementation using LEACH Protocol

5.4.3 Node Analysis and Duty Cycle

Figure 5.9 shows the comparison of FEMS with rule-based energy management system. The constant duty cycle is presented only for comparison and is obtained by dividing the total RF energy harvested by 600, i.e., the total number of frames in five hours. It can be observed that rule-based duty cycle changes rapidly between two extremities as compared to FEMS. It is worth mentioning that the dips (zero duty cycle) for FEMS and rule-based technique correspond to sleep states during which a node hibernates, suspending all its activities and only revives once the stored energy in the buffer exceeds threshold energy $E_{threshold}$.

Figure 5.9 Duty Cycle Comparison

Figure 5.10(b) depicts the instances of sleep state during the simulation period of five hours. It can be observed that the sleep state occurrence for rule-based system is almost thirty times higher than that of FEMS. Also, the number of frames for which a node remains in an active state is greater in FEMS than Rule-Based, as shown in Figure 5.10(a). In fact, for FEMS, active frames covered almost 98% of the total observed period compared to 56% for rule-based. Budget over allocation is when the buffer does not hold the anticipated energy level to power the allocated node activities. An efficient energy management system enhances the performance of WSN by minimizing the instances of over allocation. Figure 5.10(c) shows a

considerably higher number of over allocations for rule-based than FEMS. The cases of over allocation were observed in 82% and 2% frames for rule-based and FEMS, respectively.

Figure 5.10 Node Analysis

5.4.4 Buffer Capacity and Energy Usage

Figure 5.11 Buffer Charge Comparison and Harvested Energy

Figure 5.11 shows the buffer charge level and harvested energy profile for the period of the first 30 minutes. It can be seen that some energy is wasted for the constant duty cycle policy due to buffer overcharge between time-slots 1000 and 1300. This is caused due to the non-

adaptive nature of the policy. On the other hand, such phenomena is not seen for FEMS and the rule-based approach. The other observation made was the familiar dip in the buffer charge profile for rule-based, which corresponds to the sleep state. Buffer capacity or buffer size is another crucial parameter that affects sensor nodes' form factor and cost. From the simulation data, it can be deduce that the optimum buffer capacity required to avoid overcharge is 84% of B_{max} for the rule-based system, which is more significant when compared to 74% of B_{max} for FEMS.

5.4.5 Network Performance

This section presents network-level observations for both energy management schemes. The simulation was performed for various network nodes: $n=20$, $n=50$, $n=100$ and $n=200$. Figure 5.12 shows the number of dead nodes for each round/frame for the duration of the first two hours. It can be observed that the dead node number is much higher in rule-based than in FEMS. Table 5.4 presents an average number of dead nodes for both schemes for varying n values.

Figure 5.12 Dead Nodes Comparison (for $n=100$)

Table 5.4 Average Dead Nodes

Scheme	n	Average Dead Nodes (per frame)
FEMS	20	1
	50	5
	100	14
	200	51
Rule Based	20	7
	50	34
	100	82
	200	179

Figure 5.13 Data Loss and Network Life Comparison

The network performance was also compared in terms of data loss and network lifetime. Figure 5.13(a) shows the percentage of data loss for each energy management policy. Data loss measures the difference between the data packets sent by individual nodes in a cluster and the packets received by the cluster head. It can be observed that data loss is significantly lower for FEMS than rule-based system for all four network settings. It can be perceived that the data loss increases with n for both schemes. This can be attributed to the fact that with n the network area also increases, increasing the relative distance between nodes. The increased gap demands a higher transmissions/reception power hence depleting a node of its stored energy faster. This eventually causes a higher data loss. Figure 5.13(b) compares the network lifetime for the two systems. The network lifetime is assumed to be the duration for which the number of dead

nodes remains lower than 20% of the total nodes in the network. It can be observed that FEMS enjoys a healthier lifetime than rule-based.

5.5 Summary

This chapter presents a fuzzy-based energy management system (FEMS) for RF-powered wireless sensor networks. The proposed technique utilizes a fuzzy inference system with buffer charge level and harvested energy forecast as its inputs. The measure of energy budget thus obtained as output is used to estimate duty cycling for individual sensor nodes.

FEMS performance was compared with rule-based Scheme. For FEMS, active frames covered almost 98% of the total observed period compared to 56% for Rule-Based Scheme. Moreover, sleep state occurrences for rule-based system is thirty times higher than that of FEMS. Additionally, much lower events of over-allocation were observed for FEMS and it was also deduced that the optimum buffer capacity required to avoid overcharge is 10% lower for FEMS than for rule-based Scheme. Low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) protocol was deployed for network implementation and to evaluate FEMS's network performance. The dead nodes number was found to be much higher in rule-based than in FEMS for a varying number of network nodes. It was also observed that FEMS has superior performance in terms of data loss and network lifetime than rule-based scheme.

Chapter 6

Energy Management with Multi-Node Prediction

This chapter presents a multi-node prediction-based fuzzy energy management system (FEMS) and compares its performance with FEMS utilizing a single node prediction approach for varying prediction intervals. The multi-node prediction method utilizes energy readings from neighbouring nodes to estimate future energy availability, unlike the single-node procedure, which forecasts energy utilizing its own historical data only. Predicted energy values and buffer charge levels are fed to the energy management system to obtain an adaptive duty cycling for optimal energy utilization. The results show that multi-node prediction increases the sensor node's active period and reduces the network's overall data loss. It is also observed that FEMS deploying multi-node prediction shows superior performance for shorter prediction intervals than FEMS with single node prediction.

6.1 Introduction

Chapter 5 presented a fuzzy-based energy management system - FEMS, which utilizes buffer charge level and harvested energy forecast to dynamically adjust individual sensor node's duty cycling and sleep-active schedule. It was also observed that FEMS significantly improved the sensor network's lifetime and reduced data loss demanding a smaller energy buffer size. For harvested energy prediction, we implemented an exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA) based single node prediction approach, which endows satisfactory performance in terms of prediction error. In light of the observation that the efficacy of a prediction based energy management system largely depends on the accuracy of the energy prediction method (Kansal et al., 2007, Moser et al., 2010, Jushi et al., 2016), the single-node prediction method is replaced with multi-node prediction approach to determine the effect on the behaviour of the energy management system and in the network's performance at large.

Figure 6.1 Fuzzy Based Energy Management using Single-Node Prediction

Figure 6.2 Fuzzy Based Energy Management using Multi-Node Prediction

Multi-node energy prediction technique or simply multi-node energy predictor has been discussed in Chapter 4. Comparing its performance with single-node energy predictor, the multi-node energy predictor is found to have comparable or less prediction error for various prediction intervals. Figures 6.1 and 6.2 show FEMS utilizing single-node and multi-node energy predictor, respectively. The effect of prediction on FEMS performance is analysed for varying prediction intervals of 10 seconds and 30 seconds. The two systems are compared in terms of their duty cycle, sleep/active state and instances of over allocation. Moreover, observation is also made for the stored energy profile to determine the individual buffer capacity, which each system demands. Finally, low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) protocol is adopted for network implementation and to evaluate the sensor network's performance for the two prediction approaches.

6.2 System Description

Figure 6.1 depicts an energy management system utilizing the single-node prediction method. This method predicts the future energy availability using the energy harvesting history of a single node. The fuzzy-based energy management system uses the predicted energy along with buffer charge level to determine the optimum duty cycling rate. The system shown in Figure 6.2 uses the exact energy management mechanism; however it is equipped with a multi-node energy predictor. The multi-node energy prediction approach considers the energy harvesting histories of neighbouring nodes and uses this information to estimate the energy for the upcoming time frame. Both systems utilize a harvest-store-use mechanism. A sensor node harvests energy from a nearby RF source(s), stores the energy in a buffer (rechargeable battery or super-capacitor), and uses the stored energy to power the node. For simplicity, an ideal charge storing device of maximum capacity, B_{max} is considered. The energy management system estimates the energy budget for the next time frame, considering the current buffer charge level and predicted harvested energy for the upcoming time frame. A duty cycle is established based on the allocated budget for the node (load) to operate accordingly.

As described in Chapter 5, a node enters in sleep state if its buffer charge level is less than the threshold energy $E_{threshold}$. The sleep state is assumed to be of fixed period T_{sleep} during which a node suspends all activities except harvesting energy from the source and storing it in the buffer. The active state comprises frames with a duration equal to the prediction interval. Energy prediction for the upcoming frame is made at the end of each frame.

6.2.1 Single-Node Prediction

The single-node prediction approach uses the EWMA model, which weighs the recent observations more than the older values. For this, a weighting factor, $0 < \alpha < 1$, is used as

exponentially decreasing weight on the past values to do a forecast (Prema and Rao, 2015, Nau, 2014).

6.2.2 Multi Node Prediction

Figure 6.3 Node Layout for Multi-Node Prediction

Figure 6.4 Frame Structure

As explained in Chapter 4, the multi-node prediction model is based on the notion that there is significant variation in the magnitude of harvested RF energy even among the nodes in close vicinity. This phenomenon is due to the propagation characteristics of the RF signal, and the degree of variation mainly depends on the frequency of the RF signal (Visser and Vullers, 2013). Figure 6.3 shows nodes of an RF-EH sensor network, with node A surrounded by four nodes, namely node 1, node 2, node 3 and node 4.

The RF energy harvested by node A at any time instance can be predicted using the harvesting history of node A and its surrounding nodes. Figure 6.4 shows the prediction time frame with

τ as the time duration between two consecutive predictions (prediction interval) and $t, t+\tau, t+2\tau$ up to $t+N\tau$ as prediction instances. The energy estimation for node A is carried out by assuming that all four neighbouring nodes hold location-based information, which is used to calculate the estimated energy using a suitable radio wave propagation model for centre node A with respect to its adjacent nodes. Future energy availability is predicted using the estimated energy for node A corresponding to each neighbouring node for instance $t+\tau$. In this way, five different versions of predictions for node A for all prediction instances will be available for four surrounding nodes. Next, the node with the least prediction error is chosen as the reference node for prediction instance $t+2\tau$ and so on.

6.3 System Simulation

To simulate the harvested RF energy, a source with an omni-directional antenna and sinusoidal impulse response is considered as described in Chapter 5. Free-space path loss model is utilized for estimating energy loss during signal propagation. Exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA) technique is used for single-node prediction and multi-node method to predict the harvested RF energy, as discussed in Chapter 4. Likewise, maximum buffer capacity B_{max} and consumed energy E_{load} are calculated using guidelines stated in Chapter 5 to maintain energy neutral operation (ENO). For a prediction interval of 30 seconds, both T_{sleep} and frame duration are assumed to be thirty seconds, with one frame consisting of thirty time-slots. Similarly, for a prediction interval of 10 seconds, both T_{sleep} and frame duration are taken to be ten seconds with one frame consisting of ten time-slots. The fuzzy-based energy management system (FEMS) parameters are considered per Section 5.3.1 of Chapter 5.

6.3.1 Single-Node and Multi-Node Prediction Parameters

EWMA technique with a weighing factor, $\alpha=0.4$ is utilized for single node prediction. Multi-node prediction is implemented using the node layout presented in Figure 6.3. Table 6.1 below details the simulation parameters for the multi-node prediction scheme.

Table 6.1 Multi-Node Parameters

Parameter	Value
d_1	1 m
d_2	2.5 m
d_3	5 m
d_4	7 m
θ_{12}	60°
θ_{23}	40°
θ_{34}	20°
θ_{41}	240°

Mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) is a widely used measure for prediction accuracy for various prediction schemes. Table 6.2 presents the MAPE for both single and multi-node prediction approaches for prediction intervals of 10 seconds and 30 seconds.

Table 6.2 Prediction Errors for Single-Node and Multi-Node Prediction

Prediction Interval	MAP Error	
	Single-Node	Multi-Node
10 sec	31.93	32.24
30 sec	17.87	17.83

6.3.2 Network Parameters

LEACH protocol is implemented to evaluate and to compare fuzzy-based energy management systems utilizing single-node and multi-node prediction approaches. Table 6.3 presents the network parameters. The network deployment area varies with the number of sensor nodes n

in the network. For $n=20$, the network area is set to be $20*20 m^2$, and for $n=50$, the deployment area is $50*50 m^2$.

Table 6.3 WSN Parameters

Parameter	Value
Deployment areas	$20*20 m^2$ and $50*50 m^2$
Number of nodes	20 and 50
Data packet size	50 bytes
Energy dissipated in Tx/Rx	50 nJ/bit
Base station location	Outside WSN area

6.3.3 Node Analysis and Duty Cycle

Figure 6.5 Duty Cycle Comparison for Prediction Interval of 10 seconds

Figure 6.6 Duty Cycle Comparison for Prediction Interval of 30 seconds

Figures 6.5 and 6.6 show a comparison of single-node and multi-node prediction systems for prediction intervals of 10 seconds and 30 seconds, respectively. For 30 seconds intervals, the average duty cycle is found to be 44.27% and 44.32% per frame for single node and multi-

node prediction techniques, respectively. Similarly, it was observed to be 44.16% and 44.24% duty cycling for 10 seconds intervals. It is worth mentioning that the dips (zero duty cycle) in the duty cycle correspond to sleep states during which a node hibernates, suspending all its activities and only revives once the energy stored in the buffer exceeds the threshold energy level. It was also analysed that the number of dips for 10 seconds interval are significantly higher than that of 30 seconds, which can be attributed to the differing prediction accuracies for the two intervals. It is already discussed in Chapter 4 that prediction error increases with the decrease in prediction interval, and consequently, this leads to the degraded performance of the energy management system.

Figure 6.7 Node Analysis for Prediction Interval of 10 seconds

Figure 6.8 Node Analysis for Prediction Interval of 30 seconds

Figures 6.7 and 6.8 depict node performance parameters during the simulation period of five hours. The sleep state occurrence for single-node prediction is observed to be 1.8 times higher

than multi-node for 30 seconds intervals while almost 1.2 times higher for 10 seconds intervals. Also, the number of frames for which a node remains active is greater for multi-node for both the prediction intervals. Multi-node active frames covered almost 99% for 30 seconds intervals and 96% for 10 seconds intervals compared to 98% and 95% for respective time intervals. Budget over allocation is when the buffer does not hold the anticipated energy level to power the allocated node activities. An efficient energy management system enhances the performance of WSN by minimizing the instances of over allocation. Figures 6.7 (c) and 6.8 (c) show more over-allocations for single-node compared to multi-node prediction. It was also observed that the cases of over-allocation in 2.5% frames for single node for both 30 seconds and 10 seconds intervals while for the multi-node the over allocations are none and 1% for same intervals.

6.3.4 Buffer Capacity and Energy Usage

Figure 6.9 Buffer Charge Comparison for Prediction Interval of 10 seconds

Figure 6.10 Buffer Charge Comparison for Prediction Interval of 30 seconds

Buffer charge profiles for both the intervals are shown in Figures 6.9 and 6.10. The familiar dip is observed in the buffer charge graphs, which corresponds to the sleep state. For 10 seconds interval, complete buffer discharge (buffer charge level below threshold) can be noticed in 42 time-slots for single node prediction compared to 14 time-slots for multi node prediction. None of the time-slots suffered the same phenomenon for multi node while only 15 cases were found for single node for 30 seconds interval. From the simulation data, it can also be deduced that the optimum buffer capacity required to avoid overcharge for both the single and multi-node systems to be similar.

6.3.5 Network Performance

In this section, network-level observations are presented for both energy management systems. The simulation was performed for the varying number of network nodes: $n=20$ and $n=50$. Figures 6.11 and 6.12 show the number of dead nodes for each round/frame. It can be observed that the average number of dead nodes is higher in single-node than in multi-node for 10 seconds prediction interval. In comparison, the numbers are comparable for 30 seconds intervals. Table 6.4 presents the average number of dead nodes for both systems for varying n values.

Figure 6.11 Dead Nodes Comparison for Prediction Interval of 10 seconds

Figure 6.12 Dead Nodes Comparison for Prediction Interval of 30 seconds

Table 6.4 Average Dead Nodes

System	n	Average Dead Nodes (per frame)	
		10 Sec Interval	30 Sec Interval
Single Node	20	6	1
	50	31	5
Multi Node	20	5	1
	50	29	4

Figure 6.13 Data Loss Comparison for Prediction Interval of 10 seconds

Figure 6.14 Data Loss Comparison for Prediction Interval of 30 seconds

Comparison of network performance in terms of data loss was also performed. Figures 6.13 and 6.14 show the percentage of data loss for the energy management systems utilizing different prediction approaches. Data loss measures the difference between the data packets sent by individual nodes in a cluster and the packets received by the cluster head. It can be observed that data loss is lower for multi-node prediction method for both the network settings. It can be observed that the data loss increases with n for both schemes. This can be attributed to the fact that with n , the network area expands, increasing the relative distance between nodes. The increased distance demands a higher transmissions/reception power hence depleting a node of its stored energy faster. This eventually causes a higher data loss.

6.4 Summary

This chapter presents a multi-node prediction-based energy management system and compares its performance with FEMS utilizing a single-node prediction approach, explained in Chapter 5. The multi-node prediction method utilizes energy readings from neighbouring nodes to estimate future energy availability, unlike the single-node process, which forecasts the energy

based only on its own historical data. Predicted energy values and buffer charge levels are fed to the energy management system to obtain an adaptive duty cycling for optimal energy utilization.

The multi-node FEMS is compared with single-node FEMS for varying prediction intervals of 10 and 30 seconds. It was observed that for the multi-node method, active frames covered almost 99% for 30 seconds intervals and 96% for 10 seconds intervals compared to 98% and 95% for respective time intervals for the single-node approach. Moreover, sleep state occurrences for single node prediction are 1.8 times higher than multi-node for 30 seconds intervals while almost 1.2 times higher for 10 seconds intervals. Additionally, lower events of over-allocation was observed for FEMS deploying multi-node than single-node prediction. LEACH protocol was adapted for network implementation and network performance was evaluated for both systems. Number of dead nodes was found to be higher in single-node than in multi-node approach for varying network nodes. FEMS utilizing multi-node was found to have superior performance in terms of data loss than single-node prediction approach.

Chapter 7

Summary, Observations and Conclusions, and Future Works

In this chapter, the thesis is concluded by providing a summary of the accomplishments. In addition, this chapter also present some conclusions and future works in this area of research.

7.1 Summary

In this thesis, RF energy harvesting technique is introduced by exploring the state of the art of the current systems embracing the technology and presenting the harvester model, which was utilized to develop an energy management system coupled with a novel energy prediction method for efficient energy utilization in RF powered wireless sensor networks. Chapter 2, presents a detailed literature review of research works encompassing energy harvesting technologies and management techniques of the harvested energy in sensor networks. Moreover, various design aspects, techniques and protocols related to energy harvesting networks and the evolving paradigm of prediction-based energy management systems and their applicability in energy harvesting devices have also been presented. From the review it was observed that many researchers had proposed different models for energy harvesting networks based on solar energy, wind energy, vibration/kinetic energy and others. However, RF energy harvesting systems differ from other energy harvesting types. The amount of harvested energy depends on the parameters like source-harvester separation, RF frequency, signal interference, and the surrounding conditions. It was aimed to accommodate these parameters while developing the RF energy harvester model in Chapter 3. Another aspect of the energy harvesting system is energy prediction, which is essential in knowing the amount of energy likely to be harvested in the future. Various energy prediction techniques have been proposed and being researched. These prediction models are often coupled with energy management policies to ensure optimal network performance. To devise an RF energy specific prediction model, first the characteristics of RF energy were exploited. A multi-node prediction method was then formulated, which is applicable to RF energy harvesting sensor networks, detailed in Chapter 4. Finally, it comes to the energy management scheme, which plays a crucial role in ensuring energy neutrality while maintaining equal energy distribution among nodes so that the network's lifetime is prolonged without compromising information sensing and transmitting

rates along with other network parameters. As RF energy varies significantly within a short period it becomes crucial to develop a prudent and robust energy management technique for RF powered WSNs. For this, a fuzzy-based energy management system (FEMS) was designed and presented in Chapter 5, utilizing buffer charge level and harvested energy forecast to implement adaptive duty cycling for individual sensor nodes. Further, the performance of the FEMS was optimized by integrating it with the multi-node energy prediction method, which has been explained in Chapter 6.

7.2 Observations and Conclusions

The review of the past works shows that there has been significant research done regarding the modelling of energy harvesting networks. However, most of the works focus on solar and wind energy harvesting networks. Unlike other energy forms, RF energy harvesting depends on specific factors such as source frequency, the distance between source and harvester, ambient conditions and interference. To address this issue, the proposed RF energy harvester model described in Chapter 3 incorporated source-harvester separation distance, source frequency and ambient condition as additional parameters, which made it possible to study and to analyse the effect of these variables on optimum energy consumption rate and buffer capacity. An algorithm was developed to find the optimum energy consumption rate and buffer size for a given harvesting rate based on the model. The model was verified by analysing the simultaneous changes in consumption rate and buffer capacity due to changes in source energy rate. It was found that for the lower values of consumption rate, the increase in lifetime was minimal. Still, the corresponding buffer sizes were much larger, up to 180%, than the buffer size for the optimum energy consumption rate. On the other hand, though the buffer sizes for consumption rates higher than the optimum rate were smaller by 50% to 90%, the network

lifetime was significantly reduced by 95%. Overall, the observations indicated that the optimum energy consumption rate offers a higher WSN lifetime for relatively lower buffer capacity. The extended lifetime can be attributed to the balanced state between the energy harvesting rate and the optimum energy consumption rate resulting in minimum energy wastage.

The capability of the developed model to consider only one RF source at a time can be taken as its limitation. In practice, there can be many RF sources with different frequencies. Moreover, these RF sources can interfere with each other resulting in areas with abruptly varying magnitudes. A more comprehensive model accommodating these parameters is likely to capture the real scenario even better. Section 7.3 explains how these current limitations can form a basis for future work.

Unlike prediction for other energy harvesting systems such as solar and wind, RF energy prediction can utilize the inherent nature of RF energy, which causes it to vary within small distances. The developed multi-node energy prediction method considered the harvesting history of all nodes surrounding the central node for which energy prediction is to be made. The predicted values corresponding to each node were calculated and matched with the actual harvested energy. The node giving the least error was taken as the reference node for the next prediction, in a way such that the reference was switched from one node to another for each prediction based on the prediction error. The results were then compared with moving average based prediction approaches utilizing single-node prediction. It was observed that the multi-node method better followed the energy profile with less prediction error. Also, the multi-node prediction approach displayed enhanced performance for smaller prediction intervals. It was also demonstrated that the mathematical model formulated to compute the optimum value of prediction interval is crucial in ensuring a satisfactory prediction accuracy and a timely prediction before a node runs out of its energy.

Further, an energy management system was designed that would ensure efficient energy utilization in RF powered sensor nodes. The designed system, named as fuzzy energy management system (FEMS), consists of a fuzzy inference system (FIS), which provides budget estimates with stored charge level and energy forecast as inputs to implement adaptive duty cycling for individual nodes. Low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) protocol was adapted for network implementation and the FEMS's network performance was compared with traditional rule based energy management technique. Node analysis of the designed FEMS revealed that the sleep state occurrence for rule based system was almost thirty times higher than that of FEMS while active frames covered almost 98% of the total observed period as compared to 56% for rule based. Also, the observed cases of over allocation were 82% and 2% of the total frames for rule based and FEMS respectively. Additionally, it was found that the optimum buffer capacity required to avoid overcharge was 84% of maximum buffer size for rule based system, which is larger when compared to 74% of maximum buffer size for FEMS. For network implementation, LEACH protocol was utilized and it was found that the number of dead nodes to be much higher in rule based than in FEMS. Moreover, FEMS showed superior performance in terms of data loss and network life-time than rule-based scheme.

Overall it was found that the proposed scheme, FEMS, well adapted to the changes in buffer charge levels and harvested energy predictions, enabling the sensor node to dynamically adjust its duty cycling and sleep-active pattern for a robust operation. It was also analysed that FEMS improved the network's lifetime and significantly reduced data loss compared to the rule-based approach. In addition, FEMS demanded a smaller buffer capacity, aiding in reducing the size and cost of a sensor node implementation.

Finally, the performance of the FEMS was enhanced by coupling it with the multi-node energy predictor and its performance was also compared with single node FEMS for varying prediction

intervals. The simulation results showed that multi-node prediction increases the sensor node's active period and reduces the network's overall data loss. Additionally, it was seen that FEMS deploying multi-node prediction showed superior performance for shorter prediction intervals than FEMS with the single-node forecast.

7.3 Future Works

Although this research work has answered several questions related to modelling, energy prediction and energy management for the RF energy harvesting systems, it has also opened up several other questions and further research opportunities. In the subsections below, high-level descriptions of such research possibilities are presented.

7.3.1 RF Energy Harvester Model and Multiple Energy Sources

Chapter 3 discussed the RF energy harvester model, which constituted parameters such as the source-harvester separation distance, source frequency, ambient condition and harvester efficiency, energy harvesting, and load consumption rate. Though the model considered all the crucial RF specific parameters, it only accommodated a single frequency energy source. In a practical scenario, there can be more than one energy source with various frequencies. Also, for RF waves, path-loss depends on the frequency of the particular wave so that the source frequency could affect the amount of energy harvested. Thus, the inclusion of the multiple frequency sources in the harvester modelling makes it more diverse in application and improves its performance and accuracy.

The other potential improvement can be achieved by considering the aspect of interference. In a multiple frequency environment, there is always a chance of RF signals of similar frequency

interfering with each other resulting in spots with high and low magnitudes very close to one another. In such a scenario, though adjacent, two RF energy harvesting sensor nodes could be harvesting energy with a vast disparity in magnitude. This can only be modelled correctly if the interference component is considered in the RF energy harvester model.

7.3.2 Use of Prediction Error in Energy Management

Figure 7.1 Improving Energy Management using Prediction Error

In Chapters 5, a fuzzy-based energy management system for RF powered wireless sensor networks was described. The performance of the energy management system depends on the accuracy of the energy predictor, which was observed in Chapter 6. Hence, if the prediction error is low, one can expect an improved performance than for a high prediction error. However, if a mechanism is developed such that the contribution of predicted harvested energy in the fuzzy inference system (FIS) can be increased or decreased according to the magnitude of prediction error, it is likely to improve the system's overall performance.

Figure 7.1 shows the energy management system based on fuzzy logic for RF energy harvesting wireless sensor networks. The FIS estimates the energy budget for the upcoming time slot with

inputs as buffer-charge level and predicted harvested energy. The harvested energy prediction error is fed to the FIS, which tunes the weight of predicted harvested energy, i.e. if the error is high, the weight is downgraded and vice versa. This is to ensure that the error in prediction does not considerably affect the performance of the proposed energy management system.

7.3.3 Applicability of the Developed Models for other EH Systems

There is a possible avenue for the prediction and energy management models, which was presented in the preceding chapters, to be used with other EH systems such as solar or wind-powered WSN nodes. It would open a new paradigm of research and be equally interesting to observe the effects on the performance of the systems.

The proposed Multi-Node energy prediction approach described in Chapter 4 is basically devised for RF-EH systems for which there is a significant difference in the amount of harvested energy among the adjacent nodes. However, this prediction scheme can be helpful for solar-powered WSN nodes in cases where the solar energy incident on the nearby nodes varies significantly with time. One such situation could be mobile solar nodes. The motion of the nodes makes it challenging for the traditional energy prediction techniques to forecast energy availability by monitoring the harvesting history of a single node only. In such a scenario, the multi-node energy prediction method could enhance the prediction accuracy. Similarly, the fuzzy-based energy management system (FEMS), presented in Chapter 5, shows improved adaptability and robustness compared to the rule-based energy management system. These characteristics can be suitable for the EH system with a high rate of fluctuations in the harvested energy.

References

- Akbas, A., Yildiz, H. U., Tavli, B. and Uludag, S. (2016) 'Joint optimization of transmission power level and packet size for WSN lifetime maximization', *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 16(12), pp. 5084-5094.
- Aoudia, F. A., Gautier, M. and Berder, O. 'Fuzzy power management for energy harvesting Wireless Sensor Nodes'. *2016 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*, 22-27 May 2016, 1-6.
- Azeem, M. F. (2012) *Fuzzy Inference System: Theory and Applications*. BoD–Books on Demand.
- Azmat, F., Chen, Y. and Stocks, N. (2016) 'Predictive Modelling of RF Energy for Wireless Powered Communications', *IEEE Communications Letters*, 20(1), pp. 173-176.
- Baroudi, U. 'Management of RF Energy Harvesting: A Survey'. *2019 16th International Multi-Conference on Systems, Signals & Devices (SSD)*, 21-24 March 2019, 44-49.
- Basagni, S., Naderi, M. Y., Petrioli, C. and Spenza, D. (2013) 'Wireless Sensor Networks with Energy Harvesting', *Mobile Ad Hoc Networking: The Cutting Edge Direction* Hoboken NJ USA: Wiley, pp. 701-736.
- Bergonzini, C., Brunelli, D. and Benini, L. 'Algorithms for harvested energy prediction in batteryless wireless sensor networks'. *2009 3rd International Workshop on Advances in sensors and Interfaces*, 25-26 June 2009, 144-149.
- Bi, S., Ho, C. K. and Zhang, R. (2015) 'Wireless powered communication: opportunities and challenges', *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 53(4), pp. 117-125.

- Brown, W. C. (1984) 'The history of power transmission by radio waves', *IEEE Transactions on microwave theory and techniques*, 32(9), pp. 1230-1242.
- Cammarano, A., Petrioli, C. and Spenza, D. 'Pro-Energy: A novel energy prediction model for solar and wind energy-harvesting wireless sensor networks'. *2012 IEEE 9th International Conference on Mobile Ad-Hoc and Sensor Systems (MASS 2012)*, 8-11 Oct. 2012, 75-83.
- Cammarano, A., Petrioli, C. and Spenza, D. (2016) 'Online energy harvesting prediction in environmentally powered wireless sensor networks', *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 16(17), pp. 6793-6804.
- Castagnetti, A., Pegatoquet, A., Belleudy, C. and Auguin, M. (2012) 'A framework for modeling and simulating energy harvesting WSN nodes with efficient power management policies', *EURASIP Journal on Embedded Systems*, 2012(1), pp. 8.
- Chaour, I., Fakhfakh, A. and Kanoun, O. (2017) 'Enhanced Passive RF-DC Converter Circuit Efficiency for Low RF Energy Harvesting', *Sensors*, 17(3), pp. 546.
- Chen, J., Li, J. and Lai, T. H. (2013) 'Trapping Mobile Targets in Wireless Sensor Networks: An Energy-Efficient Perspective', *IEEE Trans. Vehicular Technology*, 62(7), pp. 3287-3300.
- Collotta, M., Pau, G. and Maniscalco, V. (2017) 'A Fuzzy Logic Approach by Using Particle Swarm Optimization for Effective Energy Management in IWSNs', *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 64(12), pp. 9496-9506.
- Costanzo, A., Dionigi, M., Masotti, D., Mongiardo, M., Monti, G., Tarricone, L. and Sorrentino, R. (2014) 'Electromagnetic Energy Harvesting and Wireless Power Transmission: A Unified Approach', *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 102(11), pp. 1692-1711.
- Eu, Z. A., Tan, H.-P. and Seah, W. K. G. (2011) 'Design and performance analysis of MAC schemes for Wireless Sensor Networks Powered by Ambient Energy Harvesting', *Ad Hoc Networks*, 9(3), pp. 300-323.
- Fafoutis, X. and Dragoni, N. 'ODMAC: an on-demand MAC protocol for energy harvesting - wireless sensor networks', *Proceedings of the 8th ACM Symposium on Performance*

- evaluation of wireless ad hoc, sensor, and ubiquitous networks*, Miami, Florida, USA. 2069072: ACM, 49-56.
- Gilbert, J. M. and Balouchi, F. (2008) 'Comparison of energy harvesting systems for wireless sensor networks', *International Journal of automation and computing*, 5(4), pp. 334-347.
- Iannello, F., Simeone, O. and Spagnolini, U. (2012) 'Medium Access Control Protocols for Wireless Sensor Networks with Energy Harvesting', *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 60(5), pp. 1381-1389.
- Jaeho, K. and Jang-Won, L. 'Energy adaptive MAC protocol for wireless sensor networks with RF energy transfer'. *2011 Third International Conference on Ubiquitous and Future Networks (ICUFN)*, 15-17 June 2011, 89-94.
- Jung, J. W. and Weitnauer, M. A. (2013) 'On using cooperative routing for lifetime optimization of multi-hop wireless sensor networks: Analysis and guidelines', *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 61(8), pp. 3413-3423.
- Jurdak, R. (2007) *Wireless ad hoc and sensor networks: A cross-layer design perspective*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Jushi, A., Pegatoquet, A. and Le, T. N. 'Wind Energy Harvesting for Autonomous Wireless Sensor Networks'. *2016 Euromicro Conference on Digital System Design (DSD)*, Aug. 31 2016-Sept. 2 2016, 301-308.
- Kamalinejad, P., Mahapatra, C., Sheng, Z., Mirabbasi, S., Leung, V. C. M. and Guan, Y. L. (2015) 'Wireless energy harvesting for the Internet of Things', *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 53(6), pp. 102-108.
- Kansal, A., Hsu, J., Zahedi, S. and Srivastava, M. B. (2007) 'Power management in energy harvesting sensor networks', *ACM Trans. Embed. Comput. Syst.*, 6(4), pp. 32.
- Kansal, A. and Srivastava, M. B. 'An environmental energy harvesting framework for sensor networks', *Proceedings of the 2003 international symposium on Low power electronics and design*, Seoul, Korea. 871624: ACM, 481-486.

- Kim, S., Vyas, R., Bito, J., Niotaki, K., Collado, A., Georgiadis, A. and Tentzeris, M. M. (2014) 'Ambient RF Energy-Harvesting Technologies for Self-Sustainable Standalone Wireless Sensor Platforms', *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 102(11), pp. 1649-1666.
- Kosunalp, S. (2017) 'An energy prediction algorithm for wind-powered wireless sensor networks with energy harvesting', *Energy*, 139, pp. 1275-1280.
- Lu, X., Wang, P., Niyato, D. and Han, Z. (2015a) 'Resource allocation in wireless networks with RF energy harvesting and transfer', *IEEE Network*, 29(6), pp. 68-75.
- Lu, X., Wang, P., Niyato, D., Kim, D. I. and Han, Z. (2015b) 'Wireless Networks With RF Energy Harvesting: A Contemporary Survey', *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 17(2), pp. 757-789.
- Mansourkiaie, F., Ismail, L. S., Elfouly, T. M. and Ahmed, M. H. (2017) 'Maximizing Lifetime in Wireless Sensor Network for Structural Health Monitoring With and Without Energy Harvesting', *IEEE Access*, 5, pp. 2383-2395.
- Morsi, R., Michalopoulos, D. S. and Schober, R. 'Performance analysis of wireless powered communication with finite/infinite energy storage'. *2015 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*, 8-12 June 2015, 2469-2475.
- Moser, C., Thiele, L., Brunelli, D. and Benini, L. (2010) 'Adaptive Power Management for Environmentally Powered Systems', *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 59(4), pp. 478-491.
- Mouapi, A., Hakem, N. and Delisle, G. Y. (2018) 'A new approach to design of RF energy harvesting system to enslave wireless sensor networks', *ICT Express*, 4(4), pp. 228-233.
- Naderi, M. Y., Nintanavongsa, P. and Chowdhury, K. R. (2014) 'RF-MAC: A Medium Access Control Protocol for Re-Chargeable Sensor Networks Powered by Wireless Energy Harvesting', *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 13(7), pp. 3926-3937.
- Najimi, M., Ebrahimzadeh, A., Andargoli, S. M. H. and Fallahi, A. (2014) 'Lifetime maximization in cognitive sensor networks based on the node selection', *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 14(7), pp. 2376-2383.

- Nau, R. (2014) 'Forecasting with moving averages', *Fuqua School of Business, Duke University*, pp. 1-3.
- Nintanavongsa, P., Doost-Mohammady, R., Di Felice, M. and Chowdhury, K. (2013) 'Device characterization and cross-layer protocol design for RF energy harvesting sensors', *Pervasive and Mobile Computing*, 9(1), pp. 120-131.
- Nishimoto, H., Kawahara, Y. and Asami, T. 'Prototype implementation of ambient RF energy harvesting wireless sensor networks'. *2010 IEEE Sensors*, 1-4 Nov. 2010, 1282-1287.
- Olgun, U., Chen, C. c. and Volakis, J. L. (2012) 'Design of an efficient ambient WiFi energy harvesting system', *IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation*, 6(11), pp. 1200-1206.
- Pau, G. and Salerno, V. M. (2019) 'Wireless sensor networks for smart homes: A fuzzy-based solution for an energy-effective duty cycle', *Electronics*, 8(2), pp. 131.
- Pimentel, D. and Musilek, P. 'Power management with energy harvesting devices'. *CCECE 2010*, 2-5 May 2010, 1-4.
- Piñuela, M., Mitcheson, P. D. and Lucyszyn, S. (2013) 'Ambient RF Energy Harvesting in Urban and Semi-Urban Environments', *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, 61(7), pp. 2715-2726.
- Piorno, J. R., Bergonzini, C., Atienza, D. and Rosing, T. S. 'Prediction and management in energy harvested wireless sensor nodes'. *2009 1st International Conference on Wireless Communication, Vehicular Technology, Information Theory and Aerospace & Electronic Systems Technology*, 17-20 May 2009, 6-10.
- Prema, V. and Rao, K. U. (2015) 'Development of statistical time series models for solar power prediction', *Renewable Energy*, 83, pp. 100-109.
- Qi, N., Dai, K., Yi, F., Wang, X., You, Z. and Zhao, J. (2019) 'An Adaptive Energy Management Strategy to Extend Battery Lifetime of Solar Powered Wireless Sensor Nodes', *IEEE Access*, 7, pp. 88289-88300.
- Rodway, J. and Musilek, P. (2017) 'Harvesting-aware energy management for environmental monitoring WSN', *Energies*, 10(5), pp. 607.

- Salarian, H., Chin, K.-W. and Naghdy, F. (2014) 'An energy-efficient mobile-sink path selection strategy for wireless sensor networks', *IEEE Transactions on vehicular technology*, 63(5), pp. 2407-2419.
- Seah, W. K. G. and Olds, J. P. 'Data delivery scheme for Wireless Sensor Network powered by RF energy harvesting'. *2013 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*, 7-10 April 2013, 1498-1503.
- Singh, S. K., Kumar, P. and Singh, J. P. (2017) 'A Survey on Successors of LEACH Protocol', *IEEE Access*, 5, pp. 4298-4328.
- Stojmenovic, I. (2005) *Handbook of sensor networks: algorithms and architectures*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Suganthi, L., Iniyan, S. and Samuel, A. A. (2015) 'Applications of fuzzy logic in renewable energy systems – A review', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 48, pp. 585-607.
- Valenta, C. R. and Durgin, G. D. (2014) 'Harvesting Wireless Power: Survey of Energy-Harvester Conversion Efficiency in Far-Field, Wireless Power Transfer Systems', *IEEE Microwave Magazine*, 15(4), pp. 108-120.
- Veilleux, S., Almaghasilah, A., Abedi, A. and Wilkerson, D. 'Stochastic modelling of wireless energy transfer'. *2017 IEEE International Conference on Wireless for Space and Extreme Environments (WiSEE)*: IEEE, 153-155.
- Visser, H. J. and Vullers, R. J. M. 'Wireless sensors remotely powered by RF energy'. *2012 6th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EUCAP)*, 26-30 March 2012, 1-4.
- Visser, H. J. and Vullers, R. J. M. (2013) 'RF Energy Harvesting and Transport for Wireless Sensor Network Applications: Principles and Requirements', *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 101(6), pp. 1410-1423.
- Vuran, M. C. and Akyildiz, I. F. (2010) 'XLP: A cross-layer protocol for efficient communication in wireless sensor networks', *IEEE transactions on mobile computing*, 9(11), pp. 1578-1591.

- Watfa, M. K., AlHassanieh, H. and Selman, S. (2011) 'Multi-Hop Wireless Energy Transfer in WSNs', *IEEE Communications Letters*, 15(12), pp. 1275-1277.
- WP3K, I.-R. (1999) 'Draft revision of recommendation ITU-R P. 1238; Propagation data and prediction models for the planning of indoor radio communication systems and radio local area networks in the frequency range 900MHz to 100GHz', *ITU-R Document 3/53*.
- Zahid Kausar, A. S. M., Reza, A. W., Saleh, M. U. and Ramiah, H. (2014) 'Energizing wireless sensor networks by energy harvesting systems: Scopes, challenges and approaches', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 38(Supplement C), pp. 973-989.
- Zhu, B., Chen, M.-y., Wade, N. and Ran, L. (2012) 'A prediction model for wind farm power generation based on fuzzy modeling', *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 12, pp. 122-129.
- Zou, T., Lin, S., Feng, Q. and Chen, Y. (2016) 'Energy-efficient control with harvesting predictions for solar-powered wireless sensor networks', *Sensors*, 16(1), pp. 53.